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Adoptive cell therapy with macrophage-drug conjugates facilitates cytotoxic drug transfer and immune activation in glioblastoma models

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One Sentence Summary: Macrophage-drug conjugate displays high antitumor activity against glioblastoma by delivering cytotoxic payload and inducing immune activation.

Abstract

The treatment of solid tumors faces substantial hurdles because of inadequate drug delivery and the immunosuppressive tumor microenvironment. To address these challenges, we developed a therapeutic platform using macrophages loaded with ferritin-drug conjugates, referred to as macrophage-drug conjugates (MDC) and applied it to glioblastoma, an immunologically cold solid tumor. MDC loaded with ferritin-conjugated monomethyl auristatin E enabled efficient, cell contact-dependent transfer of the payload by a mechanism involving transfer of iron-binding proteins, from either mouse or human macrophages preferentially into glioma cells. This targeted delivery and therapeutic efficacy was demonstrated across in vitro coculture systems, ex vivo assays using dissociated glioblastoma patient tumor samples, and in vivo using orthotopic glioblastoma mouse models, all while maintaining a favorable preclinical safety profile evidenced by minimal systemic toxicity and localized drug biodistribution. Beyond direct tumor cell killing leading to significant tumor regression and prolonged survival in these models, MDC therapy reprogrammed the immunosuppressive tumor microenvironment. Immune profiling by spectral flow cytometry revealed enhanced infiltration and activation of cytotoxic T lymphocytes and B lymphocytes while reducing immunosuppressive regulatory T cells. This culminated in a robust, durable, T cell-dependent antitumor immune response, the necessity of which was confirmed through studies in immunodeficient mouse models and by lymphocyte depletion, and which conferred protection against tumor rechallenge. The combined cytotoxic and immunomodulatory effects highlight the potential of MDC therapy as a promising strategy for glioblastoma treatment and support its further clinical development.

INTRODUCTION

Glioblastoma is the most common and most aggressive primary brain tumor in adults (1). Patients with this tumor have a poor prognosis and there is an unmet medical need for more efficacious therapies. Persistent challenges include overcoming an immunosuppressive and tumor-promoting microenvironment and achieving safe and effective delivery of potent drugs to the tumor (2,3). The challenging tumor microenvironment is, in part, a consequence of the unique brain compartment. While growing in the brain, glioma cells recruit peripheral immune cells, particularly monocyte-derived macrophages, a phenomenon also observed in other solid tumors. These nonneoplastic cells constitute a substantial proportion of the cells within the tumor microenvironment, accounting for up to 40 to 50% (4,5). These macrophages constantly interact with glioma cells (6,7), which provides a strong rationale for macrophage-based therapies against challenging solid tumors such as glioblastoma. Current therapeutic strategies encompass the use of antibodies or small molecules to repolarize macrophages toward their antitumor functions, to inhibit their infiltration, or to deplete them (8). Concrete examples are the inhibition of C-C chemokine receptor type 2 (CCR-2) or Colony Stimulating Factor 1 Receptor (9). However, the latter failed to demonstrate activity in a phase 2 clinical trial for patients with recurrent glioblastoma (10). Other approaches involve *ex vivo* engineering of macrophages to express chimeric antigen receptors or cytokines and then to re-inject them back to the patients (11). These adoptive transfer strategies hold promise as an anticancer treatment because macrophages can be expanded to large numbers and modified in versatile ways. These developments have progressed to early clinical trials for various solid tumors (12).

Another challenge in glioblastoma, as in many solid tumors, is the efficient and safe delivery of highly cytotoxic drugs. This is of paramount importance because many drugs demonstrate potent antitumor activity *in vitro* but their clinical application is often hindered by either extratumoral toxicity or poor distribution within the tumor (13). Current strategies to address these challenges encompass the use of nanocarriers or antibody-fusion proteins (14,15). One promising nanocarrier for targeted delivery is ferritin, which is biocompatible and biodegradable. Ferritin has a cage-like structure that enables the encapsulation or surface conjugation of payloads. However, in previously used administration strategies, its distribution within solid tumors relies on passive diffusion and remains limited (16).

In this study, we leveraged a recently described mechanism involving the transfer of iron-binding proteins (TRAIN) from macrophages to cancer cells to develop an adoptive cell therapy based on macrophage-drug conjugates (MDCs) (17) for glioblastoma treatment. We demonstrate the antitumor potential of this therapeutic approach against glioblastoma using

advanced preclinical *in vitro* and *in vivo* models, achieving safe and efficient delivery of highly cytotoxic payloads into the cancer cells. MDCs after cancer cell killing, phagocytosed cancer cell debris, activated immune response and reprogrammed the immunosuppressive microenvironment into an immunologically active state, triggering a strong and durable antitumor immune response. We also explored combination strategies and the mechanisms governing the transfer of ferritin-conjugates from macrophages to glioma cells. MDCs represent a versatile platform that demonstrate a dual mechanism of action, integrating targeted cytotoxicity with immune activation and offering a promising strategy for treating challenging solid tumors.

RESULTS

Macrophages transfer ferritin conjugates to glioma cells, and MDCs exhibit potent antiglioma activity in vitro

To explore whether ferritin can be transferred from macrophages to glioma cells, we used two types of macrophages, murine bone marrow-derived macrophages (BMDMs) and human blood monocyte-derived macrophages (HMDMs). These macrophages were 'loaded' with heavy chain ferritin (HFt) which was fluorescently labeled with Alexa Fluor 488 (AF488) for visualization by incubating macrophages in vitro with medium containing the HFt-AF488 protein. After internalization of HFt-AF488 into the macrophages, we cocultured these ferritin-loaded macrophages with the murine glioma cell lines SMA-560, SMA-497, GL-261, or CT-2A (**Fig. 1A**) or the human glioma cell lines ZH-305, ZH-161, LN-308, or LN-229 (**Fig. 1B**). Flow cytometry analysis showed a strong fluorescent HFt-AF488 signal in more than 90% of the glioma cells after 24 hours of coculture, indicating high efficiency of HFt transfer from macrophages to glioma cells in vitro. Confocal microscopy further confirmed this finding and demonstrated the presence of HFt-AF488 within glioma cells (**Fig. 1, C and D**). This transfer was conserved across species and seen using not only both murine and human primary macrophages but also human induced pluripotent stem cell-derived macrophages as an alternative source for cell-therapies (**fig. S1, A to C**). Time-lapse microscopy of the kinetics of the ferritin transfer from macrophages to glioma cells revealed that approximately 50% of glioma cells had taken up ferritin within 10 hours of coculture, and saturation in ferritin uptake was reached after 20 hours (**fig. S1D**).

Next, we harnessed the transfer of HFt from macrophages to cancer cells for therapeutic purposes. We conjugated ferritin by a valine-citrulline biodegradable linker with monomethyl auristatin E (vcMMAE), a highly toxic antimitotic agent frequently used as a payload for antibody-drug conjugates (ADCs) that has also been investigated against glioblastoma (18). This resulted in an HFt-vcMMAE complex named HFt-735 (**fig. S1, E and F**). We chose MMAE for its microtubule-disrupting mechanism, which complements DNA-alkylating agents (temozolomide and lomustine) and circumvents MGMT-mediated (O-6-methylguanine-DNA methyltransferase) DNA-repair resistance in glioblastoma. The conjugation was validated through ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy (UV-Vis), dynamic light scattering, and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS). LC-MS analysis confirmed the purity of the HFt-735 conjugate, revealing that only 0.0016% of the total drug was unbound MMAE (**fig. S1F**). Loading HFt-735 into macrophages to form MDCs (MDC-735) yielded a concentration of approximately 148.98 ng of MMAE per 10^6 of human macrophages and 38.98 ng for BMDMs (**fig. S1G**). We also investigated the release of

MMAE by cleavage of the valine-citrulline linker by the cancer cell abundant protease, cathepsin B after macrophage-mediated transfer of HFt-735 to tumor cells (**fig. S1, H and I**). Cathepsin B expression was required in glioma cells for cytotoxicity, confirming the dependence of the linker on this enzyme for MMAE release (**fig. S1, H and I**). Coculture of HFt-735-loaded murine (**Fig. 1E**) or human monocyte-derived macrophages (**Fig. 1, F and G**) with species-matched glioma cells reduced glioma cell viability in a time and concentration-dependent manner. The glioma cells in these cultures exhibited disrupted microtubules (**Fig. 1H**) and the subsequent formation of multinucleated cells as a result of improper spindle formation and cytokinesis (**fig. S1J**), affirming the antimitotic drug effect of MMAE. To confirm conjugate integrity within macrophages, HFt was dually conjugated with: AF488 for direct visualization of HFt; and with vcMMAE. Confocal microscopy then validated the intracellular co-localization of the AF488 signal from HFt with MMAE (detected using an anti-MMAE antibody), indicating that the HFt-vcMMAE conjugate remained intact (**fig. S1K**). Macrophages loaded with HFt without the drug did not exhibit antitumor activity compared with those loaded with the therapeutically effective HFt-735 (**fig. S1L**).

Time-lapse microscopy revealed that the viability of HFt-735-loaded macrophages decreased at a slower rate than cancer cells (**Fig. 1G**). These data suggest a window of time for macrophages to deliver the toxic payload to cancer cells while avoiding long-term persistence. In addition to this cytotoxic effect, we also observed stronger phagocytic activity of MDC-735 compared with control macrophages (**fig. S1, M to O**). Time-lapse microscopy captured the dynamic process of phagocytosis of CT-2A- zsGreen glioma cell fragments and debris by murine MDC-735 over a 48-hour coculture period (movies **S1** and **S2**), and imaging flow cytometry confirmed the internalization of CT-2A- zsGreen inside the macrophages (**fig. S1N**). Further in vitro studies revealed that MDC-735 coculture exhibited superior glioma cell killing, compared with free MMAE or MMAE conjugated to bovine serum albumin (BSA) (**fig. S2, A and B**). These results demonstrated that conjugation of MMAE and HFt and loading the complex to macrophages is essential for therapeutic efficacy).

Promising antiglioma activity of intratumorally administered MDCs in orthotopic syngeneic and xenograft glioma mouse models

To investigate the transfer of ferritin from macrophages to glioma cells and the therapeutic potential of MDCs in vivo, we used immunocompetent mice bearing orthotopic gliomas. We implanted fluorescently labeled GL-261-iRFP720 murine glioma cells into the brain and after 7 and 11 days, we administered murine macrophages that were loaded ex vivo

with HFt-AF790 or cell-free HFt-AF790, either intratumorally or intravenously (**Fig. 2A** and **fig. S3, A to C**). Ex vivo flow cytometry (**fig. S3D**) and microscopy (**Fig. 2B**) showed the presence of an HFt-AF790 signal specifically in the iRFP720 positive and CD45 negative glioma cells, confirming the in vivo transfer of ferritin from macrophages to glioma cells. In vivo imaging using fluorescence molecular tomography (FMT) revealed that the intratumoral administration of macrophages loaded with fluorescently-labeled ferritin resulted in detection of the ferritin signal solely in the brain tumor area. Conversely, intravenous administration led to a ferritin signal in the liver and lung for both macrophage-HFt-AF790 and free HFt-AF790. However, in the tumor area, the signal was detected only with macrophage-HFt-AF790 and not with free HFt-AF790 (**fig. S3, A to D**), indicating that the macrophage-based approach is favorable for tumor targeting. However, intratumoral administration is the most efficient route to get a high effector cell number to the tumor site, making it the currently preferred administration route for cell therapies against glioblastoma (19,20).

Flow cytometry was used to check whether loading BMDMs with HFt-735 to generate MDC-735 might skew the cells toward an M2-like phenotype, which is typically associated with immunosuppression and tumor promotion. To address this, we compared the phenotype of MDC-735 to that of monocytes and empty BMDMs (M0 macrophages). There were no significant differences in surface marker expression between M0 macrophages and MDC-735 (**fig. S3, E and F**), suggesting that drug loading did not induce an M2 polarization. MDC-735 retained robust antitumor activity even in the presence of immunosuppressive, human M2-like macrophages (M2A and M2C), indicating its therapeutic potential within highly immunosuppressive tumor microenvironments (**fig. S3, G and H**).

To better understand the distribution and therapeutic impact of MDC-735, we conducted an experiment using an organotypic glioblastoma brain slice model (**fig. S4A**). This model demonstrated that MDC-735 cells were able to penetrate the tumor and deliver the 735 drug to the tumor cells more effectively compared with the administration of free components (a mixture of macrophages, HFt, and 735 drug) (**Fig. 2C** and **fig. S4, B to D**). Moreover, in the MDC-735 treated group, the tumor ex vivo was smaller than in the group treated with a mix of free macrophages, HFt, and 735 drug (**fig. S4E**). This result underscores the necessity of loading macrophages with the HFt-735 complex instead of treating macrophages with free HFt and free 735 drug.

Next, we assessed the therapeutic potential of MDC-735 in two orthotopic, immunocompetent murine glioma models, GL-261 and CT-2A (**Fig. 2, D to F**). Unloaded macrophages and free HFt-735 served as a control. Free MMAE has been reported to be lethal upon administration to mice (21) and therefore cannot be used as a free drug, but can serve as

a highly potent payload usually in a form of an ADC or a protein-drug conjugate (22). Although we also observed toxicity of the cell-free HFt-735 complex and no antitumor activity of the unloaded macrophages, the treatment with MDC-735 was well tolerated, reduced the tumor growth and conferred a survival benefit compared with controls (**Fig. 2, E and F**). We explored this further in a therapeutic-window experiment, in which CT-2A-bearing mice received one or two injections of MDC-735 at varying dose levels to determine the minimum effective and maximum tolerated doses balancing antitumor efficacy and safety (**fig. S5A**). Tumor size analysis showed a reduced tumor perimeter compared with the phosphate-buffered saline (PBS)-treated group (**fig. S5, B and C**). Administration of two injections of 2×10^6 MDC-735, the highest dose tested, led to improved survival outcomes as compared with a single treatment in CT-2A-bearing mice (**fig. S5, D and E**). Half of the group (three animals of six) achieved long-term survival. The magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of three randomly selected animals from the PBS-treated and MDC-735 treated (two administrations of 2×10^6) groups on day 20 confirmed the presence of the tumor in all of the PBS-treated groups and in one animal of the MDC-735 treated group. In a group treated with one injection of 1×10^6 MDC-735, one animal of six achieved long-term survival, whereas in a group treated with two injections of 0.5×10^6 MDC-735 two animals of six achieved long-term survival (**fig. S5, D and E**). This experiment suggests that optimal macrophage dose is important for maximizing the therapeutic outcome.

In CT-2A model, we introduced additional controls. We investigated the antitumor activity of intratumorally administered macrophages loaded with free MMAE and additionally, we investigated the antitumor activity of intratumorally administered BSA-MMAE complex. None of these groups conferred a survival benefit as observed with MDC-735 confirming that macrophage loading of HFt-735 has the most promising antiglioma activity (**fig. S5, F and G**).

MDC-735 also demonstrated a long-term antitumor effect, where five of six mice survived initial treatment of CT-2A gliomas (2×10^6 MDC-735), and of those, four (out of five) remained tumor-free after rechallenging 6 months later with glioma cells implanted in the contralateral hemisphere, without further therapy (**Fig. 2G**). This finding suggests the involvement of the immune system as a part of the response to MDC-735 treatment and induction of durable antitumor effect and induction of the immune resistance against glioma.

To investigate the translational potential of macrophage-ferritin drug conjugates for the treatment of glioblastoma, we examined the safety and efficacy of large-scale produced and cryopreserved human macrophages loaded with HFt-735 (MDC-735) in mice bearing orthotopic human ZH-161 glioma. We differentiated macrophages from monocytes isolated

by leukapheresis from healthy donors using the CliniMACS Prodigy (Miltenyi) automated cell processing platform. These cells were then loaded with HfT-735 to create MDC-735 and cryopreserved until use. Flow cytometry demonstrated that the macrophage markers CD14, 25f9 and SR-A1 did not differ between control macrophages and MDC-735. However, MDC-735 expressed less of the immunosuppressive and phagocytosis inhibitory marker SIRP α compared with unloaded macrophages (**fig. S3, E and F**). We injected MDC-735 intratumorally into ZH-161-iRFP720 glioma-bearing mice on days 7 and 14 after tumor cell implantation. We monitored tumor growth by *in vivo* imaging using FMT (**Fig. 2H**). The treatment was well tolerated, reduced tumor growth, and conferred a survival benefit, with four of six mice achieving long-term survival (**Fig. 2I and fig. S6, A and B**). These data demonstrate the therapeutic activity and feasibility of MDC-735 as a cryopreserved, readily available treatment, highlighting its potential for development in clinical applications.

MDC-735 has a promising preclinical safety profile

To assess the safety of MDC-735, we first investigated the cytotoxicity against cancer cells or nonmalignant primary cells in cocultures *in vitro*. After 72 hours of coculture, MDC-735 preferentially reduced the viability of LN-229 glioma cells compared with nonmalignant primary astrocytes, primary hippocampal neurons, or primary human corneal epithelial cells (**Fig. 2J**), which are the cells known to be affected by MMAE-related toxicity in patients.

We assessed the safety profile *in vivo* by evaluating biodistribution, blood cell counts, and blood biochemistry measures. Biodistribution analysis of the MMAE payload in different organs of orthotopic glioma-bearing mice treated with intratumoral administration of MDC-735 demonstrated that MMAE was detectable only in the brain over eight time points up to 72 hours. In other tissues, its concentration was below the lower limit of quantification (**Fig. 2K**). Analysis of blood cell counts did not reveal any alterations in red blood cells, white blood cells, or platelets upon intratumoral MDC-735 treatment measured 7 or 28 days after injection. The concentration of the kidney function marker creatinine and liver function markers alanine aminotransferase and total bilirubin remained unchanged (**Fig. 2L**), as did other blood counts (**table S1**). To further confirm the safety of intratumoral MDC-735, we measured anti-MMAE drug antibodies (ADAs) in the blood 7 and 28 days after intratumoral MDC-735 administration. ADA concentrations were below the detection range (**Fig. 2M**), indicating no immune response against the therapeutic payload in the circulation. Similar results were obtained in healthy mice that did not carry gliomas but were intracranially

injected with MDC-735, suggesting that there is no systemic toxicity of MDC-735 (**table S1** and **fig. S6, C and D**). Furthermore, *ex vivo* histopathological evaluation of various mouse tissues showed that the injected macrophages (CD68⁺ cells) were present only in the brain tumor region 7 days after intratumoral MDC-735 treatment. However, by day 28, macrophages were no longer detectable in any tissue (**figs. S7 to S9**), indicating their relatively short lifespan. No organ abnormalities or morphological signs of toxicity were observed in any organ.

MDC-735 changes the tumor microenvironment and promotes a T cell-dependent antitumor immune response

Results from the rechallenge study, demonstrating durable tumor resistance in mice treated with MDC-735, suggested an immunological component of the treatment. To investigate the immunological aspects of MDC-735, we first investigated soluble pro-inflammatory cytokines and the T cell activation marker CD69 in cocultures of human LN-229 glioma cells, human unstimulated T cells, and either unloaded human monocyte-derived macrophages or human MDC-735 *in vitro*. The highest concentrations of the pro-inflammatory cytokines interleukin-6 (IL-6) and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) were detected in triple cultures with MDC-735 (**Fig. 3A**). An elevated IL-6 concentration was also detected *ex vivo* in plasma from murine CT-2A glioma-bearing mice on day 12 post-tumor implantation, 2 days after the second intratumoral MDC-735 treatment (**Fig. 3B**). Flow cytometry analysis revealed an increase in the lymphocyte activation marker CD69 in human T cells cocultured with human MDC-735 and human glioma cells compared with controls (**Fig. 3C**). Coculture of LN-229 cells with free MMAE did not activate increased CD69 expression on T cells *in vitro* (**Fig. 3C**). This result demonstrates increased CD69 expression by treatment with MDC-735 over the free drug (MMAE) in activation of T cells (**Fig. 3C**).

Subsequently, we investigated the immunological effects of MDC-735 treatment on the tumor microenvironment *in vivo* in fully immunocompetent orthotopic glioma-bearing mice. CT-2A glioma-bearing mice were treated intratumorally with PBS, plain BMDMs, cell-free Hf-735, or MDC-735 on day 7 after tumor implantation and tissue resident immune cells were subsequently analyzed on day 15 by *ex vivo* spectral flow cytometry of the tumor-bearing hemisphere as well as the tumor-draining lymph nodes (TDLNs) and non-tumor draining lymph nodes (non-TDLNs). This enabled the quantitative detection of different immune cell subsets as demonstrated in the Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (**Fig. 3D**) based on typical lineage markers (**Fig. 3E** and **fig. S10A**) and the gating

strategy (**fig. S10B** and **C**). Compared with controls, CT-2A glioma-bearing mice treated intratumorally with MDC-735 had the highest numbers of tumor-infiltrating B cells, neutrophils, and CD4 and CD8 T cells (**Fig. 3F**). Furthermore, CD8 T cells from MDC-735 treated mice exhibited the lowest expression of the exhaustion markers TOX (thymocyte selection–associated high mobility group box), CD279, and TIM-3 (T cell immunoglobulin and mucin domain–containing protein-3) (**Fig. 3G**). Also the frequency of Tim3/PD1 double-positive CD8 T cells that have impaired cytotoxic activity (**Fig. 3H**) (23) was reduced upon MDC-735 treatment (**Fig. 3I**). Collectively, these results suggest that MDC-735 treatment converts the immunosuppressive glioma tumor microenvironment into an immunologically active one.

In TDLNs, MDC-735 treated glioma-bearing mice exhibited lower numbers of regulatory T (T_{reg}) cells (**Fig. 3J**) and the PD1⁺/CD39⁺ subset of T_{reg} cells that mediate a highly immunosuppressive environment (**Fig. 3K**), whereas these populations were not meaningfully changed in the non-TDLNs (**fig. S10, D and E**). These results suggest that MDC-735 also reduces immunosuppression in the TDLNs, thereby promoting an antitumor immune response.

Given the potential of macrophages in shaping the tumor microenvironment and their potential to become tumor-associated macrophages, we also investigated the persistence of and phenotype of the intratumorally administered CD45.1⁺ macrophages, either loaded with Hft-735 or not, that could be distinguished from the endogenous immune cells based on the congenic marker system CD45.1/CD45.2 (**fig. S10F**). One week after treatment, we detected fewer MDC-735 within the tumor compared with plain BMDMs, suggesting that MDC-735 persists less (**fig. S10G**). Furthermore, we observed phenotypic differences between administered plain BMDMs and MDC-735. MDC-735 exhibited a more pro-inflammatory phenotype compared with plain BMDMs, as demonstrated by decreased expression of the immunosuppressive markers CD206, Arginase, PD-L1, and TIM-3, and increased expression of MHC-II (**fig. S10, H and I**).

These results suggest that MDC-735 stimulates antitumor immunity, promotes T-cell activation, and prevents T-cell exhaustion. To functionally prove these observations and to validate that the immunological effects of MDC-735 are important for its antitumor effects, we used immunodeficient nonobese diabetic–severe combined immunodeficient (NOD-SCID) mice lacking functional T, B, and natural killer cells and RAG1^{-/-} mice lacking functional B and T lymphocytes. The curative potential of MDC-735 in immunocompetent mice (4 out of 7 long-term survivals and 5 out of 7 long-term survivals, respectively) was abrogated in both immunodeficient mouse strains (**Fig. 3, L and M**), underscoring the critical involvement of

lymphocytes in mediating this response. Subsequent depletion experiments confirmed the relevance specifically of T cells. After CD4 and CD8 T cell depletion, which was validated by flow cytometry (**fig. S10J**), the survival benefit and curative potential of MDC-735 (three of seven long-term survivals) were abrogated (**fig. S10K**). These comprehensive analyses collectively highlight the multifaceted impact of MDC-735 on the tumor microenvironment and the antitumor immune response it induces, reinforcing its potential as a therapeutic strategy for immunologically cold glioblastoma.

Local irradiation or chemokine receptor overexpression improve the therapeutic efficacy of intravenously administered macrophages carrying ferritin-drug conjugates

In line with the lower intratumoral accumulation of MDC-735 after systemic administration compared with intratumoral administration, the survival after intravenously administered MDC-735 was less extended than after intratumoral administration and there was only one long-term surviving mouse in the CT-2A glioma model but none in the GL-261 glioma model (**Fig. 4, A to C**). However, because the intravenous administration route might be the only viable route in patients who are not eligible for intratumoral treatment, we investigated strategies to improve the migration of intravenously administered MDC-735 into orthotopically implanted gliomas to get more cells to the tumor site and to increase the antitumor effect of intravenously administered MDC-735. To achieve this, we used two strategies. First, we combined local low-dose tumor irradiation at days 6 and 10 after tumor implantation with intravenously administered MDC-735 at days 7, 9, 11 and 13 (**Fig. 4D**). Radiotherapy is a well-established glioma therapy and low-dose irradiation has been shown to promote the migration of peripheral macrophages into tumors (24). In line with this, local pre-irradiation of the tumor site with 2 x 2 Gy facilitated the migration of fluorescently labeled macrophages into the tumor (**Fig. 4E** and **fig. S11A**), thereby enhancing the antitumor activity of systemically administered MDC-735 (**Fig. 4, F to H** and **fig. S11, B and C**). In the fast-growing GL-261 model, two of six mice intravenously treated with MDC-735 achieved long-term survival.

As a second strategy, we conducted additional ex vivo engineering of macrophages and electroporated them with mRNA encoding for CCR2 (**Fig. 4, I and J**). CCR2 is a chemokine receptor that promotes macrophage migration in response to the chemokine CCL2 (25), which is overexpressed in glioma (26). After confirming that mRNA electroporation increased the cell-surface expression of CCR2 in primary murine macrophages and the cell line RAW264.7 as a control (**Fig. 4K**), we treated glioma-bearing mice with MDC-735 or MDC-735 additionally overexpressing CCR2. Macrophages overexpressing CCR2 exhibited

improved migration activity toward the tumor (**Fig. 4L and fig. S12A**) and once loaded with HFt-735, demonstrated stronger antiglioma effects (in the GL-261 model) with reduced tumor growth (**fig. S12B**) and prolonged survival. One mouse of six treated intravenously with MDC-735 achieved long-term survival (**Fig. 4M**).

The transfer of ferritin from macrophages to glioma cells depends on cell-cell contacts and involves cytoskeleton rearrangements and vesicle transfer

To elucidate the mechanisms underlying ferritin transfer from loaded macrophages to glioma cells, we investigated the requirement for cell-cell contact. For this, we employed semipermeable membranes to physically separate macrophages loaded with fluorescent HFt from glioma cells during coculture allowing molecule diffusion through the medium (**Fig. 5A**). This separation blocked the transfer, indicating a predominantly contact-dependent mechanism (**Fig. 5B**). High-resolution time-lapse microscopy confirmed direct cell-cell interactions between macrophages and glioma cells as well as the transfer of ferritin through these contact sites (**fig. S13, A and B and movies S3 and S4**). To further characterize potential underlying molecular factors governing this contact-dependent process in glioma cells, we used affinity purification of biotinylated ferritin from macrophages or glioma cells separated after coculture followed by mass spectrometry to identify binding proteins to ferritin in macrophages or glioma cells. Through iterative experiments, we consistently identified 10 potential ferritin-binding proteins in macrophages or glioma cells after coculture (**fig. S13C**). Pathway enrichment analysis of these proteins revealed that the ferritin-binding proteins in macrophages were associated with processes such as cytoskeleton organization, regulation of protein localization to the cell periphery, and vesicle fusion (**fig. S13D**). In contrast, the proteins identified to bind to ferritin in glioma cells were associated only with cytoskeleton organization. The protein stabilin-1 (STAB1) was consistently detected in both macrophages and glioma cells. To support the role of this protein in the transfer of ferritin from macrophages to glioma cells, we used CRISPR/Cas9 to knock out the gene in the mouse macrophage cell line RAW264.7 and CT-2A glioma cell line. After confirming the expected truncation of the STAB1 gene in RAW264.7 and CT-2A cell lines (**fig. S13E**), we assessed the effect of the STAB1 knockout on the uptake of HFt-AF488 by macrophages and its subsequent transfer to glioma cells in coculture. STAB1 knockout in macrophages increased the uptake of HFt-AF488 in macrophages (**fig. S13F**) and also the transfer to glioma cells, whereas STAB-1 knockout in CT-2A glioma cells had no effect (**fig. S13G**). These data supported the involvement of STAB1 in the transfer process from macrophages on a functional basis and suggest an inhibitory role for this protein.

To functionally validate whether the transfer occurs by the previously described, newly found TRAIN process (17), we used the vesicle marker CD63 and lipid membrane marker (PKH-67) to demonstrate the localization of HFt within intracellular vesicles in cancer cell (**Fig. 5C**). Furthermore, we used different inhibitors of intracellular vesicle formation and transport, like the phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase inhibitor Wortmannin, the calpain inhibitor Calpeptin, the neutral sphingomyelinase inhibitor GW4879 and the Rho kinase (ROCK) inhibitor Y-27632, which functionally validated that perturbations of intracellular vesicle formation or transport inhibit the transfer of ferritin from macrophages to glioma cells (**Fig. 5D**). Furthermore, we used imaging flow cytometry to validate a synapse-like structure forming between macrophages and cancer cells (**Fig. 5E and F**). Quantitative imaging flow cytometry revealed F-actin accumulation at the macrophage-cancer cell interface (**Fig. 5G**), indicating an immune synapse-like structure. Inhibition of F-actin polymerization (using Cytochalasin D and Lantraculin B) reduced the transfer, confirming the involvement of actin dynamics (**Fig. 5, H and I**). Overall, these results confirmed involvement of TRAIN mechanism in HFt transfer from macrophages to glioma cells.

Macrophage-ferritin-drug conjugates have high translational potential with promising antitumor activity in complex glioblastoma patient samples.

We explored the therapeutic activity of MDC-735 in complex glioblastoma patient samples directly obtained from surgery. We collected tumor samples from 20 patients with glioblastoma (**table S4**), dissociated them into single-cell suspension and cocultured these complex tumor suspensions with ready-to-use frozen allogeneic primary human macrophages loaded with either fluorescently labeled HFt-AF647 ($n = 10$ patient samples) or HFt-735 (MDC-735) ($n = 10$ patient samples) (**Fig. 6A**). After 48 hours of coculture, we used an image-based single-cell functional profiling platform to characterize the effects of MDCs at the single-cell level (27). Despite inter-patient heterogeneity, we observed a transfer of fluorescently labeled HFt from macrophages to glioma cells in 10 of 10 patient samples, with more glioma cells displaying a ferritin signal compared with nonmalignant cells from the tumor microenvironment in 8 of 10 patient cultures, suggesting a preferential transfer to cancerous cells (**Fig. 6, B and C**, and **fig. S14, A and B**).

In a separate set of 10 patient-derived dissociated tumor samples, we qualitatively assessed morphological changes in glioma cells and observed a more rounded cell shape, predominantly after MDC-735 treatment (**Fig. 6D**). To quantify phagocytic activity of macrophages, we performed a coculture of fluorescently labeled MDC-735 and Nestin⁺ labeled glioma cells. Nestin was a key marker of cancer cells, therefore was used to identify

cancer cell debris within the macrophages. Analysis was done using an automatic image analysis platform to detect colocalization of fluorescent macrophage marker and Nestin. We observed substantial phagocytosis of glioma cells by allogenic macrophages, most notably in cocultures with Hft-735-loaded macrophages across all 10 patient samples. This suggests that MDC-735 enhances macrophage effector function compared with controls, supporting its potential therapeutic efficacy (**Fig. 6E** and **fig. S14C**).

DISCUSSION

Adoptive cell therapies, particularly ex vivo engineered T cells, and ADCs with potent payloads yielded encouraging responses in extracranial malignancies (28,29). However, recent studies in patients with glioblastoma, one of the most challenging tumors, have demonstrated only limited activity (30-32). Clinical trials of immune checkpoint blockade with nivolumab in recurrent glioblastoma showed no survival benefit over bevacizumab (33). Single-agent pembrolizumab in PD-L1-positive glioblastoma achieved a weak overall response rate (33). Barriers to effective treatment include: immunosuppressive microenvironment, low mutation burden, sparse tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes (TILs) and poor drug delivery (30-32). Among nonmalignant cells, microglia and macrophages dominate the glioblastoma (GBM) microenvironment, making them logical targets for intervention or tools to be used against GBM (34, 35). Prior macrophage- focused strategies—CSF- 1R inhibition (to deplete or repolarize tumor- associated macrophages) and CCL2 blockade (to curb monocyte recruitment), ARG1/2, transforming growth factor- β , and hypoxia- inducible factor-1 α blockade—showed limited clinical efficacy, underscoring the need for novel approaches (36,37).

This study introduces the MDC “Trojan horse” strategy, as an advanced therapeutic approach, that combines targeted cytotoxicity with immune modulation by direct cell-to-cell transfer of ferritin-MMAE conjugates, avoiding nonspecific extracellular drug release (38-40). Our data supported that the efficacy of MDC-735 is driven by a newly found TRAIN mechanism involving the contact-dependent transfer of ferritin-conjugates from macrophages to glioma cells, as demonstrated previously (17). Because direct cell-to-cell contact is required to occur, highly targeted delivery and safety are ensured.

MDC-735 produced significant survival benefits in both orthotopic xenografts and immunocompetent models without detectable toxicity. Free HFt + MMAE mixtures, as well as HFt-MMAE complex (without macrophages) failed to penetrate tumors or induce cytotoxicity, whereas HFt-MMAE preloaded macrophages (MDC-735) achieved robust on-target cell death. Further results revealed bispecific mode of action of MDC-735. In addition to the direct antitumor effects, MDC-735 also demonstrated the ability to phagocytose glioma cell fragments and cellular debris. This underscores the critical role of macrophages not only in direct drug delivery but also in initiating a cascade of events leading to cancer cell killing and subsequent immune activation. HMDMs showed higher MMAE uptake than BMDMs, underpinning superior payload delivery. A two-dose intratumoral regimen further improved survival versus a single dose, emphasizing optimization of cell dose and schedule. In vivo experiments reinforced the translational potential of MDC-735, with

intratumoral administration demonstrating robust tumor shrinkage and extended survival in orthotopic glioma models (CT-2A, GL261, ZH-161). This approach drove robust and durable tumor regression and extended survival. In the CT-2A model, which exhibits mesenchymal differentiation and reduced interferon and antigen presentation pathways (characteristics akin to the aggressive mesenchymal human GBM subtype), five of six mice treated with MDC-735 survived for the entire 70-day study period. A curative effect in this model was confirmed by MRI in selected animals. To assess long-term tumor immunity, these long-term survivors were rechallenged 6 months later with implantation of CT-2A cells in the opposite hemisphere of the brain, and they resisted tumor growth, suggesting that MDC-735 not only eliminated tumors but also induced a durable, immune-mediated protective response. This suggests the potential for abscopal effects in multisite tumors, as evidenced by the long-term protection observed in rechallenged mice. Immune profiling revealed that MDC-735 treatment transformed the GBM microenvironment into an immunologically active one, marked by increased infiltration of cytotoxic T cells, B cells, reduced exhaustion markers, and lower frequencies of immunosuppressive regulatory T cells. These findings highlight the dual functionality of MDC-735 as both a cytotoxic agent and an immune modulator, making it uniquely suited for tackling immunologically cold tumors like GBM. Given the marked increase in granzyme-expressing CD8⁺ T cells and reduction in PD-1 high exhausted phenotypes post-MDC-735, combining MDC-735 with checkpoint inhibitors (e.g., anti-PD-1) could potentiate T cell effector function.

Moreover, in samples derived from patients with complex GBM obtained directly from surgical procedures, which include both cancerous and nonmalignant cells from the tumor microenvironment, MDCs displayed a preference in transferring the ferritin conjugates to cancerous cells. Cytotoxicity testing revealed higher activity against glioma cells compared with noncancerous astrocytes, hippocampal neurons, and corneal epithelial cells, supporting the specificity of the MDC-735 approach in human primary tumor samples. The preclinical safety studies provide a compelling rationale for clinical translation. MDC-735 exhibited minimal systemic toxicity, with no detectable drug release into the circulation and no adverse effects on blood counts or organ function. It is a recurring problem with MMAE-containing ADCs: such conjugates are highly potent but leak cytotoxin into the bloodstream (by cleavage prone Val Cit linkers) or damage normal tissues that express the same antigen, leading to neutropenia, neuropathy or bleeding (41-42). In contrast, our biodistribution analysis confirmed that the MMAE payload remained localized within the tumor, further supporting the safety and specificity of this approach in mice.

Although intratumoral MDC-735 was superior, systemic delivery achieved better tumor homing after either focal pre-irradiation of tumor bed or macrophage CCR2 overexpression—enhanced CCR2-CCL2 axis migration. However, recent studies showed that intratumoral treatment in GBM may provide a clinical benefit for patients. In the Phase 1 trial (NCT00805376), patients with recurrent, surgically accessible GBM were treated with a single intratumoral dose of an oncolytic virus, DNX-2401 by stereotactic biopsy needle or by implanted catheter. Objective tumor responses were observed in 72% of the needle-injected cohort, and median overall survival was 9.5 months in the needle group versus 13.0 months in the catheter group (43). Locoregional delivery of IL13R α 2-targeted CAR T cells by implantable reservoir–catheter systems has emerged as a promising strategy in GBM immunotherapy. Stable disease or better was achieved in 50% (29 of 58) of patients, with two partial responses, one complete response and a second complete response after additional CAR-T cycles off protocol. This outcome suggests that locoregional cell therapy can elicit significant antitumor activity with manageable safety profiles (44).

The preclinical safety profile, combined with potent antitumor activity, makes MDC-735 a promising candidate for treating glioblastoma, providing an avenue for delivery of drugs like MMAE, which are typically limited by systemic toxicities (45). The platform's versatility enables the conjugation of various therapeutic agents to ferritin, as demonstrated by Taciak et al. (17), where this system was shown to be readily adapted for targeting other malignancies or delivering alternative therapeutic modalities, such as small molecule inhibitors targeting specific oncogenic pathways, or even immunomodulatory agents like STING agonists, highlighting its adaptability for diverse oncological applications.

Although the results of this study are highly promising, there are a few limitations to note. The preclinical models used, including orthotopic glioma xenografts and immunocompetent mouse models, offer strong evidence of the therapeutic potential of MDC-735, although they do not fully replicate the human GBM tumor microenvironment. Similarly, even if ex vivo analyses conducted with patient-derived samples demonstrated targeted activity of MDC-735, this study does not capture the full heterogeneity of GBM and variability in therapeutic responses across different patient populations. Moreover, GBM remains one of the most treatment-resistant cancers, with profound barriers such as diffuse infiltration, rapid recurrence, and immune suppression, all of which will pose challenges even for novel approaches like MDC therapy. Future research should focus on evaluating the precise molecular mechanism of MDC-735-mediated immune activation to understand its role in T cell recruitment and reprogramming. Concurrently, it will be important to determine whether MDC-facilitated, MMAE-induced glioma cell death elicits enhanced immunogenic

cell death signature. Such studies will deepen our mechanistic understanding and may reveal novel targets for synergistic therapeutic combinations.

An additional consideration is the clinical implementation of cell-based therapies in this context. While MDC-735 uses allogeneic macrophages, their short-term lifespan and limited proliferation capacity may reduce the risk of long-term immune complications, supporting the feasibility of an off-the-shelf approach. Still, further validation in clinical settings is necessary to confirm consistent efficacy and durability of response.

In conclusion, MDCs demonstrate a functionally bispecific mechanism of action, integrating targeted cytotoxicity with immune activation. This dual-action profile is conceptually analogous to that of bispecific antibodies, which aim to bridge tumor cell recognition and immune cell engagement. This unique mechanism of action positions MDC-735 as a strong candidate for first-in-class therapy for GBM. Its favorable safety profile and ability to overcome key challenges in the tumor microenvironment further support its clinical potential. This innovative approach offers new hope not only for GBM but also for other solid tumors characterized by immunosuppressive and treatment-resistant niches.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

The primary aim of this study was to develop an adoptive transfer strategy for malignant brain tumors using macrophages loaded with iron-binding-protein cages containing therapeutic drugs, enabling targeted delivery to cancer cells. This involved verifying the specificity and efficiency of payload transfer to glioma cells using *in vitro* coculture systems, advanced microscopic visualization, and functional cytotoxicity assays. The second aim was to evaluate the translational potential of this approach using autologous and allogeneic macrophages loaded with the most efficient ferritin-drug conjugate for clinical application in patients with glioblastoma. We compared efficacy of the MDC-735 therapy *in vivo* and in patient-derived tumor *ex vivo* coculture studies. We used orthotopic glioma models, transplanting syngeneic or xenograft glioma cells into mice, to assess *in vivo* efficacy through survival studies, tumor burden monitoring, and analysis of antitumor immune responses (including immune cell profiling of tumor microenvironment and functional assays in immunodeficient models). A safety profile was generated by evaluating local and systemic drug concentrations, blood cell counts and biochemistry, and murine organ histology after treatment to support future clinical trial applications.

Power analysis was performed to determine the appropriate sample size for animal experiments aiming to detect increase in median survival. The goal was to detect an anticipated 8-day increase in median survival (e.g., from an expected 17 days for control to 25 days for treated groups, with an estimated SD of 7 days), using a Type I error rate (α) of 0.05 and 80% power ($1-\beta$; $\beta = 0.20$).

For the two *in vivo* studies using U-87 MG-luc cells, mice were randomized to treatment groups on the basis of bioluminescence signals after tumor establishment and before treatment initiation. In all other *in vivo* experiments described, mice were assigned to treatment groups cage by cage and investigators assessing the outcomes in mice were not blinded to the treatment group. The number of replicates, group sizes and statistical tests used in the analysis are indicated in the respective figure legends. Samples were excluded only if they did not meet technical requirements for downstream analyses (insufficient cell number or poor sample quality). This was the case for Fig. 3 (F, G and I to K), Fig. 6E and fig. S10 (D to E). No samples were removed on the basis of statistical outlier analysis.

Ferritin production

Cloning, expression, and purification process of the recombinant heavy chain ferritin (HFt; NCBI Reference Sequence: NP_002023.2) were provided by Genscript. The synthetic gene encoding HFt was designed to be optimal for *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) codon usage, cloned into a pET30a vector and overexpressed in *E. coli* BL21 cells (plasmid sequence provided in data file S1). After inducing cell culture, the cells were lysed, and the supernatant was purified. Purification was based on the use of hydrophobic and ion exchange chromatography. The purity of the product was checked on SDS–polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis gel. The concentration of purified protein was calculated by measuring the UV-Vis using an extinction coefficient of $18\,600\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Ferritin conjugation

To label HFt with fluorescent dyes such as AF488 and AF790, 10 mg of protein was diluted in 0.9 ml of PBS and buffered with 0.1 ml of 1 M sodium bicarbonate (pH 8.4) (Sigma-Aldrich). Alexa Fluor Nhydroxysuccinimide ester (succinimidyl ester) (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was dissolved in 50 μl of dimethyl sulfoxide (Sigma-Aldrich) and gently mixed with the HFt solution. The reaction tube was incubated for 1 hour at 25°C with continuous shaking at 500 rpm using a ThermoMixer (Eppendorf). The solution was then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm to remove any precipitate and subsequently washed using an Amicon Ultra-4 Centrifugal Filter Unit (Merck Millipore) with PBS until the ultrafiltrate was clear. The final concentration of labeled HFt was determined using UV-Vis spectrophotometry (NanoDrop 2000).

Conjugation of ferritin with drug 735 (MC-Val-Cit-PAB-MMAE, CAS No: 646502-53-6, MedChemExpress) was carried out with a fivefold excess of drug over protein. Drug 735 was purchased from a commercial supplier with a declared purity of over 99.90% in the form of a powder and dissolved in a polar solvent before the reaction. The conjugation reaction buffer and the final formulation were based on an aqueous solution with a neutral pH. To assess conjugate purity, an LC- MS method was developed and optimized to separate MMAE from the HFt-735 conjugate. Calibration standards were prepared by serially diluting an MMAE standard (MedChemExpress) in 35% acetonitrile to establish a standard curve. Samples of the HFt-735 conjugate were injected directly without additional preparation or dilution. Chromatographic peaks corresponding to free MMAE from the resulting chromatograms were integrated, quantified, and compared against the standard curve to measure free MMAE concentrations. Using the drug-to-protein ratio, determined by LC–MS, and the protein concentration of the sample, as measured by UV–Vis spectroscopy, the total MMAE

concentration in the conjugate was calculated. The ratio of free MMAE to the total MMAE (conjugated plus free) thus provides a measure of the purity of the HFt-735 conjugate preparation.

In vitro macrophage-glioma cocultures for HFt transfer and antiglioma activity

To test HFt transfer, macrophages were incubated with fluorochrome labeled HFt at 0.5 mg/ml in non-supplemented DMEM medium for 1 hour (37°C, 5% CO₂). Acceptor cells were stained with CellTrace (Life Technologies) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Then cells were seeded at 2:1 ratio (0.4×10^6 donor cells : 0.2×10^6 acceptor cells per well) on a 24-well plate and incubated for 24 hours. Cells were detached from the plate with accutase (Sigma Aldrich), washed twice with PBS, resuspended in flow cytometry buffer and analyzed using FACSVerse (BD) flow cytometer. Results were analyzed using FlowJo 7.6.1 (BD) software. Where indicated, the 24-well Transwell (Corning) culture system was used to assess physically separated donor and acceptor cells.

To assess effect of various inhibitors on HFt transfer, HMDMs were loaded with fluorescently labeled HFt (0.5 mg/mL, 1 h) and LN-229 cancer cells were labeled with CellTrace. All inhibitors were prepared as DMSO solutions, and equivalent volumes of DMSO were used as vehicle controls in each coculture condition. Inhibitors and vehicle controls were diluted into coculture medium (RPMI + 5% FCS + 1% pen/strep) to achieve the following final concentrations: Cytochalasin D (10 μ M; MedChem Express; #HY-N6682), Latrunculin B (25 μ M; Sigma-Aldrich; #L5288-1MG), GW4869 (20 μ M; MedChem Express; #HY-19363), Wortmannin (100 μ M; Sigma-Aldrich; #W3144-250UL), Calpeptin (60 μ M; MedChem Express; #HY-100223), and Y-27632 (50 μ M; Sigma-Aldrich; #SCM075). Following loading, 0.2×10^6 HMDMs were resuspended in medium containing the respective inhibitor or vehicle control in 5 ml polystyrene tube and preincubated for 1 hour at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Subsequently, 0.1×10^6 LN-229 cells were added, and cocultures were maintained in the presence of the inhibitor for an additional 4 hours. Cells were then washed and stained with DRAQ7 for viability. During experiments involving GW4869, the inhibitor was also present during the HFt loading step, and no viability dye was applied due to interference with its fluorescence. Following incubation, HFt-AF488 fluorescence transfer to LN-229 cells was assessed by flow cytometry.

To test antiglioma activity of MDC-735 conjugate in vitro, macrophages were incubated with HFt-735 in non-supplemented DMEM medium for 1 hour (37°C, 5% CO₂) and seeded with cancer cells labeled with CellTrace at 1:1 ratio (0.1×10^6 macrophages : 0.1×10^6 cancer cells

per well) on a 24-well plate and incubated for 24-72 h. To compare the in vitro cytotoxic effects of HFt-735 and BSA-735, the BSA-vcMMAE conjugate (BSA-735) was prepared using the same protocol as HFt-735. BMDMs or HMDMs were loaded with either HFt-735 or BSA-735 at equimolar concentrations under identical incubation conditions (1 hour, 37°C, 5% CO₂ in non-supplemented DMEM). Subsequently, these loaded macrophages were cocultured with CellTrace-labeled cancer cells at a 1:1 ratio (0.1×10^6 macrophages : 0.1×10^6 cancer cells per well) in 24-well plates for 24–72 hours. After incubation, cells were detached from the plate with accutase (Sigma Aldrich), labeled with Zombie Viability dye (Biolegend) according to the manufacturers protocol, resuspended in flow cytometry buffer and analyzed using FACSVerse or FACSCanto II flow cytometer (BD) with addition of cell counting beads (#424902, Biolegend). The viability of cancer cells was calculated as a number of live cells relative to control condition.

Incucyte killing assay

HMDMs were generated as described above. After the initial 7-day differentiation, macrophages were polarized toward the M2A subtype by supplementing the medium with 100 ng/mL M-CSF (Miltenyi Biotec; #170-076-172), 20 ng/mL IL-13 (Peprotech; #200-13), and 20 ng/mL IL-4 (Peprotech; #200-04) for an additional 48 hours. For M2C polarization, macrophages received 100 ng/mL M-CSF, 10 ng/mL IL-10 (Peprotech; #200-10), and 10 ng/mL TGF- β 1 (Peprotech; #100-21C) under the same conditions. Non-polarized M0 macrophages were maintained in medium containing 100 ng/mL M-CSF only and collected at day 7. Loading of HMDMs with HFt-735 was performed in TexMACS medium (Miltenyi Biotec; #170-076-172) at a concentration of 1 mg/mL for 1 hour. Effector cells (MDC-735 or non-loaded macrophages), target cells (LN-229), and M2-like macrophages (M0, M2A, M2C) were seeded in 96-well plates at an effector-to-target-to-M2 macrophage ratio (E:T:MF) of 1:1:1, at the concentration of 1×10^4 of each cell type, in groups indicated in the respective figure. Images were acquired every hour over approximately 72 hours using a 10 \times objective on an Incucyte Live-Cell Analysis System. Data were analyzed with the corresponding Incucyte software.

In parallel, a cell-killing assay was conducted under the same conditions for the M0, M2A, and M2C tri-culture experiment. Briefly, these macrophages, along with effector and target cells, were seeded at a 1:1:1 ratio (1×10^5 cells of each type per well) in 24-well plates and incubated for 72 hours. After incubation, cells were detached with Accutase, stained with Zombie Viability dye following the manufacturer's instructions, and resuspended in flow

cytometry buffer. Samples were analyzed using a FACSVerse or FACSCanto II flow cytometer (BD) with cell counting beads. Viability of cancer cells was calculated as the number of live cells relative to the control condition.

Phagocytosis assay

MDC-735 or control BMDM (labeled with Violet CellTrace) and CT-2A-ZsGreen cells were cocultured at a 2:1 ratio (2×10^5 macrophages : 1×10^5 cancer cells) in 24-well plates for 48 hours at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Live imaging was performed using a Muvicyte fluorescent microscope, capturing DAPI, GFP, and Brightfield channels at 6-hour intervals. Images were analyzed with FIJI ImageJ software. Following incubation, cells were detached centrifuged (400 x g, 5 min), and resuspended in 50 µL for Amnis ImageStream X analysis. Single cells were gated based on aspect ratio > 0.7), and a minimum of 5×10^3 events per sample were recorded. Analysis was conducted using IDEAS 6.2 software, focusing on Violet CT and ZsGreen signals.

Animal experiments

Experiments were conducted in compliance with the guidelines set by the Swiss federal animal protection regulations and received approval from the regional veterinary authority (ZH079/2021). C57BL/6JRj (#SC-C57N-F), B6.129S7-Rag1^{tm1Mom}/J (RRID:MGI:2163461) and NOD.CB17-Prkdc^{scid} (#SM-NODS-F) male and female mice aged between 6 and 12 weeks were obtained from Janvier Labs and subsequently maintained in a pathogen-free environment at the Laboratory Animal Services Center of the University of Zurich. To determine the minimal number of animals per group, Power analysis has been performed. The data from previous experiments with CT-2A model were used with the following anticipated parameters, expected mean survival of 17 days, with estimated variance of 7 days. Power of the test was 80% indicating minimal number of animals as six per group. For intracranial implantation, GL-261 (2×10^4), GL-261 iRFP720 (4×10^4), or CT-2A-iRFP720 (8×10^4) cells were stereotactically implanted into the right striata of C57BL/6 mice whereas ZH-161-iRFP720 (8×10^4) cells were implanted into the right striata of NOD.CB17-Prkdc^{scid} mice on day 0. Daily observations were conducted for symptom emergence. Treatments were conducted either intravenously into tail vein (100 µl) or intratumorally (4 µl). MDC-735 was prepared directly before injection or prepared in advance and frozen. Differentiated macrophages were harvested, washed in PBS, resuspended in a 0.5 mg/ml solution of Hft-735 in serum-free macrophage medium and incubated for 1 hour at 37°C in a 5% CO₂ atmosphere

to allow HfT-735 uptake. After incubation, the macrophages were washed twice with PBS and resuspended at a concentration of 500×10^6 cells/ml for intratumoral injection and 50×10^6 cells/ml for intravenous injection. The schedules for these treatments are depicted in the schematics provided in the figures.

To assess potential tumor immunity in rechallenge study, the long-term survivors of CT-2A survival study as well as naïve mice as a control had tumor cells re-implanted into the opposite hemisphere of the brain. Survival of these mice were monitored without further treatment. T cell depletion experiments were performed using CD4 (clone GK1.5; #BE0003-1; BioXCell) and CD8 (clone 2.43; #BE0061; BioXCell) depletion antibodies. Depletion antibodies were intraperitoneally injected at 200 µg per mouse 1 day before tumor cell implantation and 100 µg every other 3 to 4 days. Cell depletion was confirmed by flow cytometry analysis of T-cells isolated from blood samples collected from the tongue vein.

The isolation of tumor cells and tumor-infiltrating immune cells was conducted as described previously (46). Where described, local cranial irradiation with a low dose of 2 Gy was applied at days 6 and 10 after tumor implantation using a RS 2000 (Serial # 3305) at 1 Gy/min. Mice bodies were covered with a lead plate and only the tumor implantation sites were exposed to the fractionated radiation. Tumor growth was monitored using the FMT2500 (PerkinElmer) system. Where indicated, macrophages stained *ex vivo* with a 2 µM solution of CellBrite-NIR790 (Biotium) were also detected using the FMT2500. Image data were analyzed using the TrueQuant 3.1 software (PerkinElmer).

For therapeutic window experiment, MRI was performed with a 7T imager (Bruker BioSpin) at day 20 after tumor implantation. Coronal T2-weighted images were acquired by using ParaVision 360 (Bruker BioSpin). Tumor regions were identified manually by two independent raters, and the tumor perimeter was outlined and quantified using MIPAV (11.2.0).

Female athymic nude mice aged 5 to 7 weeks were used for the drug distribution study. The mice were bred in-house by Axis Bio, all protocols used have been approved by the Axis Bioservices Animal Welfare and Ethical Review Committee (UK; project license PPL2885), and all procedures were carried out under the guidelines of the Animal Act 1986. Upon confirmation of tumor growth via U-87 MG-luc bioluminescence, mice were randomized into 7 groups ($n = 3$): untreated and six groups of mice treated with MDC-735 (single dose of 2×10^6 , intratumorally) with organ sampling point at 1, 4, 12, 24 and 72 hours after dose. The collected organs were weighted and frozen at -80°C .

Murine organotypic glioblastoma brain slice model

The coculture system of tumor spheroids and cerebellar slices was adapted from the protocol described (46). Briefly, cerebellar slices were prepared from postnatal day (P9) to P11 wild-type C57BL/6JRj mice. Sagittal slices, 350 μm in thickness, were obtained using a vibratome (VT 1200S, Leica,) and cultured on Millipore inserts (PICM 03050, Merck Millipore,) for up to 10 days. The brain slice medium described in (47), was refreshed daily.

To generate tumor spheroids, CT-2A-zsGreen cells were seeded in low-attachment, round-bottom 96-well plates (4520, Corning)) at a density of 5000 cells per well and cultured for 48 hours. For tumor-cerebellar coculture, a single tumor spheroid was carefully retrieved using a pipette and placed on top of a cerebellar slice. After 5 days of coculture, MDC-735 or mixture of BMDM, HFt and MMAE components group were prepared and microinjected to tumor.

Microinjection was performed using a manipulator equipped with a 26-gauge needle (Small Hub RN Needle, 2 in, Point Style 5, 7784-07, Hamilton). The needle was positioned at the edge of the tumor spheroid, and 2 μL of the cell mixture for each experimental group was manually injected into the cerebellar slice. Following microinjection, cerebellar slices were fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde at 24 and 48 hours for subsequent immunofluorescence analysis.

For immunofluorescence analysis, the attached insert membrane and attached cerebellar slices were carefully trimmed and transferred into a 24-well plate for staining. The slices were permeabilized by incubation in trypsin-EDTA at 37°C in a humidified incubator for 5 min. Blocking was performed by incubating the slices in PBS containing 3% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 3% BSA, and 0.3% Triton X-100 for 1 hour at room temperature. For primary antibody staining, anti-HFt (1:200) and anti-MMAE (1:25) antibodies were diluted in PBS containing 3% FBS and 3% BSA and incubated with the slices overnight at 4°C. Secondary antibodies were prepared in the same buffer (PBS containing 3% FBS and 3% BSA) and applied for 3 hours at room temperature. After thorough washing with PBS with 5% BSA, the slices were mounted using VECTASHIELD antifade mounting medium (H-1000-10, Vector Laboratories) for subsequent imaging. The image acquisition is performed using a Leica SP8 inverted confocal laser scanning microscope with 20 \times and 63 \times objectives.

Toxicology study

90 Balb/c nude (RRID:IMSR_RJ:BALB-C-NUDE) mice (45 female, 45 male; 5 to 8 weeks old, 19 to 26 g) were sourced from Axis Bioservices and housed in individually ventilated cages with ad libitum access to a certified diet and sanitized water. Conditions were controlled at 20 to 24°C, 30 to 70% humidity, with a 12-hour light/dark cycle. The study's protocols received approval from the Axis Bioservices Animal Welfare and Ethical Review Committee, (UK; project license PPL2885) adhering to the Animal (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986 guidelines. Tumor cell implantation involved intracerebrally injecting U-87 MG-luc cells (1×10^5 in 5 μ l Matrigel) into 54 mice using a 30-gauge needle. To confirm tumor growth, the animals were imaged at 1 and 2 weeks post-implantation. Mice with actively growing tumors confirmed were then randomly assigned to the treatment groups (PBS or 2.5×10^6 MDC-735 in 5 μ l; intratumoral injection for tumor bearing mice or intracerebral injection for control, healthy mice).

For blood analysis, at terminal sampling points (day 7 or day 28), blood was drawn from the tail vein of each subject for analysis. Subsequent evaluations included a complete blood count and a blood biochemistry profile. Blood samples were processed into plasma for ADA quantification. For enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, 96-well plates were precoated with MMAE-BSA (Cell Mosaic, CM52113) at a concentration of 2 μ g/well. Plasma samples from all subjects were then diluted 1:1000 in PBS and added to the wells. After washing, the wells were incubated with a horseradish peroxidase-labeled goat anti-mouse immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibody (BioLegend, 405306) and diluted to a final concentration of 0.4 μ g/ml in blocking buffer (1:2000 dilution) to detect any mouse IgG.

For Histopathology, upon termination, tissues including the brain (with tumor when applicable), femur, skin, intestines (small and large), heart, kidneys, liver, lungs, reproductive organs (ovary/testes), spleen, and stomach were harvested and embedded in paraffin blocks. Consecutive sections of 4 μ m were prepared with a microtome; one set was stained with hematoxylin and eosin for general pathology evaluation, whereas the other was stained with an anti-CD68 antibody (Cell Signaling Technology, 26042).

Drug quantification in tissue samples

MMAE quantification in tissue and blood samples were performed by LC-MS method. Quantification was made for both free MMAE and FT-bound MMAE. Samples were

homogenized by Precellys 24 tissue homogenizer (Bertin Technologies). After homogenization samples were centrifuged, supernatants were taken and stored at -80°C before analysis. For FT-bound MMAE tissue homogenates were mixed with FT-MMAE working standard solutions, ferritin heavy chain agarose slurry, and PBS with vigorous vortexing. After agarose washing, Cathepsin B treatment was performed. After incubation with cathepsin B samples were centrifuged, supernatants were blended with Internal Standard Working Solution (MMAE-d8) and, then vortexed and centrifuged. Supernatants were transferred to a glass vial with inserts for LC-MS analysis.

Lymphocyte activation

Human peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were isolated from buffy coats and T lymphocytes were enriched using the Pan T Cell Isolation Kit (Miltenyi Biotec, cat. 130-096-535) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Isolated T cells (1×10^6 per well) were cultured in 24-well plates in RPMI medium supplemented with 10% bovine calf serum (BCS), 60 ng/mL IL-2, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin and incubated for 7 days at 37°C and 5% CO_2 . HMDMs were obtained from PBMCs as described above. Monocytes were differentiated into macrophages using TexMACS medium supplemented with 100 ng/mL M-CSF and 1% penicillin/streptomycin over 7 days. HMDMs were loaded with HfT-735 (1 mg/mL) or equimolar BSA-735 solutions for 1 hour at 37°C , 5% CO_2 , to generate MDC-735 or MDC-BSA-735, respectively. For coculture experiments, T cells, LN-229 cells, and MDCs (or MDC-BSA-735) were combined at a 1:1:1 or 1:1 ratio (1×10^5 cells of each type per well) in RPMI with 10% BCS, 60 ng/mL IL-2, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin. Additional controls were used as shown on a respective figure. After 48 hours, media were collected, and adherent cells were detached using Accutase. Cells were stained with Zombie NIR viability dye, blocked with FcR Block, and labeled with FITC-conjugated anti-human CD3 (1:100; (#11-0037-42; ThermoFisher) and PE-conjugated anti-human CD69 (1:100; Invitrogen, cat. 12-0699-42). Data were acquired on a BD FACSCanto II flow cytometer.

Patient samples and image-based functional profiling of macrophages in complex glioblastoma patient samples

All samples involving humans were in accordance with the ethical guidelines outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and upon approval from the Cantonal Ethics Committee (BASEC-Nr:

2019-01721). Patients with glioblastoma were included only after their consent. Glioblastoma patient samples were collected after surgery at the University Hospital of Zurich or Basel. Details of the glioblastoma patient cohort are provided in table S4. Single-cell suspensions were obtained as previously described (4). Tumor single cell suspensions were mixed with healthy-donor derived HMDMs loaded with HfT-735 and labeled with PKH26 membrane dye in 2:1 ratio ($1 \times 10^4 : 0.5 \times 10^4$ cells) into clear-bottom, tissue-culture treated, CellCarrier-384 Ultra Microplates (Perkin Elmer, #6057300). As control groups, patient single-cell suspensions were seeded alone, with empty PKH26-labeled HMDM or with free HfT-735 in the concentration equivalent to the amount in loaded HMDMs. After 48 hours of incubation at 37°C, 5% CO₂, cells were fixed with 4% PFA (Sigma- Aldrich), blocked with PBS containing 5% FBS, 0.1% Triton X- 100, and 4',6- diamidino- 2- phenylindole (DAPI) (4 µg/ml, #422801, BioLegend) for one hour at RT and stained with Alexa Fluor 488 anti-NESTIN (Biolegend, #656812, 1:500) and Alexa Fluor 647 anti-CD45 (Biolegend, #368538, 1:300) overnight at 4°C. The 384-well plates were imaged using the Opera Phenix automated spinning-disk confocal microscope at 20x magnification (Perkin Elmer, HH14000000). Cells were segmented on the basis of the DAPI channel using CellProfiler 2.2.0. Downstream image analysis was carried out with MATLAB R2021b. Marker-positive cells counts for each condition were determined on the basis if a linear threshold of the histograms of each channel. They were averaged per condition and compared against the control groups.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using R (R Core Team 2019) with R package 'ggplot2' for data visualization (Wickham 2016) and GraphPad Prism 10. Normality of the data was assessed by the Shapiro–Wilk test. For comparisons between two groups, two-tailed unpaired or paired Student's t-tests were used. When the normality assumption was not met, the non-parametric Wilcoxon test was applied instead. For comparisons involving more than two groups, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post hoc test or two-way ANOVA followed by pairwise comparisons of estimated marginal means with Tukey correction was used, as stated in the figure legends.. The survival data from in vivo studies were analyzed using the Kaplan-Meier method to estimate survival curves for each treatment group. Differences in survival rates between groups were evaluated using the log-rank (Mantel-Cox) test. To account for the increased risk of type I error due to multiple comparisons, the Bonferroni-Hochberg correction was applied to adjust *P*-values. *P*-value less than 0.05 was regarded as significant. Results are expressed as mean ± SD unless otherwise stated. Box and

whisker plots indicate the median (middle line), 25th and 75th percentiles (box) and minimum and maximum values (whiskers). All individual-level data are available in **data file S2**.

List of Supplementary Materials

Materials and Methods

Fig. S1 to S14

Table S1 to S4

Data File S1

Data File S2

Movie S1 to S4

MDAR reproducibility checklist

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Author contributions

M.M.S., M. Bialasek, M.K. T.W. designed and performed in vitro and in vivo experiments, analyzed the data and wrote the manuscript. M.M. performed immunological ex vivo analysis. M.S.L performed organotypic glioblastoma brain slice imaging. A.B. performed the patient ex vivo profiling. I.M., B.T., M.G. P.K., D.K., W.L., M.S., J.N., J.B., K.G. performed in vitro experiments and produced the ferritin conjugates. M. Bühler analyzed the AP-MS data. S.P. helped AP-MS acquisition. M. Bialasek, L.B., B.S., M.W., M. Baumgartner, S.T., S. Pascolo,

L.R., T.P.R. and M.K. edited the manuscript. S. Pascolo generated the mRNA and G.H. acquired glioblastoma tissue and edited the manuscript.

Competing interests

M.W. has received research grants from Quercis and Versameb, and honoraria for lectures or advisory board participation or consulting from Bayer, Curevac, Medac, Neurosense, Novartis, Novocure, Orbus, Philogen, Roche and Servier. T.W. has received honoraria from Philogen. T.P.R. and MK hold equity in Cellis. M. Bialasek, B.T, I.M, T.P.R, M.K, are inventors of intellectual property related to this work (patent application numbers: PCT/EP2016/064484 (Cellular targeted active ingredient delivery system), PCT/EP2016/064483 (Cellular targeted active ingredient delivery system), PCT/PL2016/050057 (Cellular targeted pharmaceutically active substance or label delivery system), PCT/EP2021/056996 (Ferritin variants with increased stability, complexation ability and transferrin receptor affinity), PCT/EP2022/057205 (Ferritin variants with increased stability and complexation ability), EP22195466.2 (Isolated Targeted Delivery System for the Treatment of Glioma)). M. Bialasek, I.M., B.T., D.K, M.S., J.N., J.B., W.L., T.P.R, M.K are employees of Cellis. Cellis is a company pursuing the commercial development of this technology. There are no conflicts with this current research. All other authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data and materials availability: All data associated with this study are present in the paper or supplementary materials. Unique reagents used in this study are available from the authors upon request. Ferritin and ferritin-drug conjugate are available from Cellis under a material transfer agreement with Cellis. The mass spectrometry proteomics data have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium by the PRIDE (52) partner repository with the dataset identifier PXD060767.

Figures

Figure 1. Macrophages transfer HFt conjugates to glioma cells and MDC-735 has strong antiglioma activity in vitro. (A and B) Flow cytometry histograms and quantification of HFt-AF488 in murine (A) or human (B) glioma cells after coculture with HFt-AF488-loaded macrophages or unloaded control macrophages for 24 hours. Data presented as representative density plots (left) and bar plots of average geometric mean fluorescence intensity (geo-MFI) (middle), and the percentage of AF488-positive cells (right). Dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 3$ independent replicates. (C and D) Representative confocal microscopy images illustrating HFt-AF488 in the murine glioma cell lines CT-2A (top) or GL-261 (bottom) (C) or HFt-AF488 fluorescence in human glioma cell lines LN-229 (top) and ZH-161 (bottom) (D) after 24 hours of HFt-AF488-loaded macrophage coculture. Dotted box indicates inset region magnified underneath. Scale bars, 20 μm ; inset, 5 μm . (E and F) Quantification of flow cytometry analysis of glioma cell viability after 24, 48, or 72-hour coculture with macrophages loaded with varying concentrations of HFt-735 in murine (E) or human glioma cells (F). Viability is expressed as the number of live cancer cells relative to the control (0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ loading dose) condition. Dots represent individual sample replicates of $n = 3$ (E) or $n = 4$ (F), h, hours. (G) Quantification of time-lapse fluorescence microscopy analysis of viability changes in LN-229 human glioma cells (red) and HFt-735-loaded HMDMs (blue) over 72 hours of coculture, with images captured every 3 hours. $n = 3$ independent experiments based on two representative fields of view. (H) Representative confocal images demonstrating the microtubule-disrupting effects of MDC-735 on LN-229 glioma cells after 24 hours of coculture. Anti- β -tubulin staining (red); DAPI nuclear stain (blue); and CellTrace to visualize glioma cells (yellow). Scale bar, 10 μm . Data in (A, B, E, F, G) are presented as means \pm SD. Statistical analysis in (A) and (B) was performed using paired two-tailed Student's t -test and in (E) to (G) was performed using one-way ANOVA with post-hoc Tukey HSD test. ns ($P > 0.05$), not significant, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

Figure 2. Antiglioma activity and safety of intratumorally administered MDC-735 in orthotopic syngeneic and xenograft glioma mouse models. (A) Schematic of the experimental design illustrating the in vivo treatment schedule and analysis workflow for tracking fluorescent HFt conjugate-loaded macrophages in GL-261 tumor-bearing mice. IT, intratumoral; IV, intravenous. (B) Representative confocal microscopy images of brain sections from the tumor-bearing mice intratumorally treated with mouse BMDM loaded with HFt-AF488. Arrows identify HFt-AF488 that colocalizes with a non-CD45.1+ cell. White dashed box indicates magnified area below. Scale bars, 20 μm ; inset, 10 μm . (C) Representative confocal microscopy images showing a tumor cross-section in an organotypic CT-2A-zsGreen glioblastoma brain slice model after injection of BMDM-HFt-735. Arrowheads indicate the presence of anti-735 antibody signal within the tumor area after 48 hours, asterisks indicate anti-MMAE signal within macrophages. Scale bar, 50 μm . (D) Schematic outline of the survival study of glioma-bearing mice that were treated IT on days 5 and 10 after tumor implantation with murine MDC-735. Negative controls include PBS, unloaded macrophages, and cell-free HFt-735 conjugate. (E and F) Kaplan-Meier survival curves for GL-261- (E) or CT-2A (F) glioma tumor-bearing mice receiving IT treatment with murine MDC-735 or controls. $n = 6$ mice per group. (G) Survival analysis of mice surviving initial CT-2A glioma implantation (F) and rechallenged 6 months later with CT-2A cells in the contralateral hemisphere. Statistical significance was determined by Log-rank test. PBS, $n = 3$; MDC-735, $n = 5$. (H) Scheme of the experimental design using human ZH-161-iRFP720 glioma-bearing mice with human MDC-735. (I) Kaplan-Meier survival curves for ZH-161 glioma-bearing mice treated with IT-administered human MDC-735. Controls included PBS, empty HMDMs and free HFt-735 conjugate. $n = 6$ mice per group. (J) Viability analysis of primary astrocytes, corneal epithelial cells, hippocampal neurons, and LN-229 glioma cells by flow cytometry after 72-hour coculture with MDC-735. Data are expressed as means \pm SD relative to control. Dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 3$ independent replicates. (K) Concentration of MMAE in tissues at multiple time points after MDC-735 injection into the mouse brain. $n = 3$ per time point. (L and M) Hematology and serum chemistry profiles (L) and antidrug antibody (ADA) concentrations (M) in plasma of human glioma-bearing mice after IT MDC-735 or PBS treatment. Dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 6$ mice per group. Gray area represents normal concentrations for each parameter. Survival data [(E), (F), (G) and (I)] were analyzed using the Log-rank test. One-way ANOVA with Tukey HSD post hoc test was used for multiple group comparisons in (J), (L) and (M). For all panels, ns ($P > 0.05$), not significant, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$. Schematic illustrations in (A), (D), and (H) were created with BioRender.

Figure 3. MDCs change the tumor microenvironment and promote a T-cell dependent antitumor immune response. (A) Secreted IL-6 and TNF- α concentration in a 48-hour in vitro coculture of LN-229 glioma cells and T cells with MDC-735 or unloaded human MDMs as control. Data are presented as means \pm SD; dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 3$. (B) IL-6 concentration in peripheral blood plasma of CT-2A tumor-bearing C57BL/6 mice after IT MDC-735 or PBS treatment. Dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 5$ per group. (C) CD69 expression on T cells, assessed by flow cytometry after 72 hour coculture with LN-229 glioma cells and MDC-735, compared with control groups. Data are presented as means \pm SD; dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 3$. (D) Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) plot showing 12,000 cells per sample from each of the 17 mice, used for visualization of immune cell populations, identified by spectral flow cytometry, in dissociated CT-2A tumor-bearing brain hemispheres from C57BL/6 mice treated with PBS, BMDM, HFt-735 or MDC-735. (E) Heatmap displaying key lineage marker expression across immune populations identified in (D). (F) Box plots comparing immune cell proportions across PBS (control), plain BMDMs, free HFt-735, or MDC-735 treatment. Dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 4$ or 5 per group. (G) CD8+ T-cell exhaustion marker expression across the treatment groups from (F). Dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 4$ or 5 per group. (H and I) Density scatter plot of TIM3 and PD1 (H) and quantification of the proportion of CD8+ T cells expressing PD1 versus TIM3. (I) Dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 4$ or 5 per group. (J) Proportion of T_{reg} cells in the TDLNs across treatment groups. Dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 4$ or 5 per group. (K) CD39 and PD1 expression on T_{reg} cells, along with the proportion of CD39+/PD1+ T_{reg} cells in the TDLNs. Dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 4$ or 5 per group. (L and M) Kaplan-Meier curves of CT-2A glioma-bearing mice treated IT with MDC-735 or PBS in immunocompetent C57BL/6 mice (L) and immunodeficient NOD-SCID (M) or RAG^{-/-} mice. $n = 7$ per group. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA and Tukey HSD post hoc test (A), two-way ANOVA with Tukey post hoc test (C), unpaired two-tailed Student's *t*-test (B), Wilcoxon unpaired test (F), (G), (I), (J) and (K) and Log-rank test [(L) and (M)]. For all panels, ns ($P > 0.05$), not significant * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$, **** $P < 0.0001$.

Figure 4. Local irradiation or chemokine receptor overexpression improve the therapeutic efficacy of intravenously administered macrophages carrying ferritin-drug conjugates. (A) Schematic of the in vivo survival study design with IV administration of MDC-735 on days 5, 7, 10, and 12 after tumor cell implantation. (B and C) Kaplan-Meier survival curves for (B) GL-261 and (C) CT-2A glioma tumor-bearing mice treated IV with MDC-735 or controls. $n = 6$ per group. (D) Schematic of low-dose irradiation (IR) schedule (days 6 and 10) for combination therapy with IV-injected MDC-735 cells (days 7, 9, 11, 13). (E) FMT quantification of intratumoral BMDM or MDC-735 accumulation. FMT, fluorescence molecular tomography. (F) FMT quantification of GL-261-iRFP720 fluorescent tumor signal as a measurement of tumor burden. Data in (E and F) represent means \pm SD; dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 6$ mice per group. (G and H) Kaplan-Meier survival curves for GL-261-iRFP720 tumor-bearing mice treated with MDC-735, free HfT-735, unloaded BMDM, or PBS alone (G) or in combination with low-dose IR therapy (H). $n = 6$ per group. (I) Schematic diagram of the plasmid used for CCR2-encoding mRNA production. (J) Schematic of the in vivo survival study using macrophages electroporated with CCR2-encoding mRNA. (K) Flow cytometry histograms and analysis of RAW264.7 and BMDMs electroporated with CCR2 mRNA, mock-electroporated (Mock Control), or untreated (Control). (L) FMT quantification of fluorescence within a brain regions of interest (ROI) from MDC-735 and CCR2-overexpressing MDC-735 macrophages. Data represent means \pm SD, dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 6$ mice per group. (M) Kaplan-Meier survival curves for GL-261-iRFP720 tumor-bearing mice treated IV with CCR2-overexpressing MDC-735, MDC-735, empty BMDM (both CCR2-expressing and non-expressing), or PBS. $n = 6$ mice per group. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey HSD post hoc test [(E), (F) and (L)] and Log-rank test [(B), (C), (G), (H) and (M)]. For all panels, ns ($P > 0.05$), not significant; $*P < 0.05$, $**P < 0.01$. Schematic illustrations in (A), (D) and (J) were created with BioRender.

Figure 5. The transfer of ferritin from macrophages to glioma cells depends on cell-cell contacts and involves cytoskeleton rearrangements and vesicle transfer. (A) Schematic representation of the in vitro coculture experiment setup. (B) Flow cytometry analysis of HFt-AF488 fluorescence in murine CT-2A (left) and human LN-229 glioma cells (right) after 24 hours of coculture with HFt-AF488-loaded macrophages. Data are presented as means \pm SD; dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 3$ independent replicates. (C) Representative confocal microscopy images showing HFt-AF488 fluorescence in LN-229 cancer cells (CellTrace Violet) after 24-hour coculture with PKH67-labeled HMDM-HFt-AF488 and anti-CD63 staining. Arrowheads highlight co-localization of AF488, PKH67, and CD63. Scale bar, 10 μ m. (D) Flow cytometry analysis of relative AF488 MFI in glioma cancer cells after coculture with HFt-AF488-loaded macrophages, in the presence of inhibitors targeting vesicle formation and trafficking pathways. Data represent means \pm SD; dots represent individual sample replicates. $n = 3$ independent replicates. (E) Representative imaging flow cytometry images of HMDM-HFt-AF488 and LN-229 cells (CellTrace Violet) stained with Phalloidin-iFluor 555 for F-actin visualization. Scale bar, 7 μ m. (F) Schematic representation of fluorescence quantification regions of interest (ROIs): macrophage ROI, cancer cell ROI, and cell-cell interaction site ROI. (G) HFt-AF488 fluorescence in each ROI defined in (F), based on imaging flow cytometry. Box and whiskers plots indicate the median and minimum and up to the maximum value. Data points represent fluorescence measurements from $n = 100$ representative images pooled from three independent replicates. (H and I) Relative AF488 MFI in cancer cells treated with (H) Latrunculin B or (I) Cytochalasin D, inhibitors of actin polymerization, compared with vehicle control. Data represent means \pm SD. Dots represent individual $n = 3$ independent replicates. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test [(B), (D) and (G)] or unpaired two-tailed Student's *t*-test [(H) and (I)]. For all panels, ns ($P > 0.05$), not significant, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$. Schematic illustrations in (A) and (F) were created with BioRender.

Figure 6. MDCs have high translational potential in complex patient samples. (A)

Schematic representation of the experimental setup. Dissociated human glioblastoma samples ($n=20$ patient samples) were cocultured with HFt-AF647-loaded HMDMs ($n = 10$ patient samples, top) or with MDC-735 ($n = 10$ patient samples, bottom). **(B)** Representative immunofluorescence images showing HFt-AF647 transfer to Nestin⁺ glioma cells. Arrowheads mark the HFt within Nestin⁺ cells. White dashed box indicates location of magnified image below. Scale bar, 50 μm , inset, 10 μm . **(C)** Quantification of HFt-AF647 transfer into tumor versus non-tumor cells in dissociated glioblastoma samples. Data represent means \pm SD; dots represent technical replicates. $n = 4$ technical replicates per patient sample; $N = 10$ biological replicates, shown individually. Statistical analysis was performed using unpaired, two-tailed Student's t test. **(D)** Representative immunofluorescence images of Nestin⁺ tumor cells cocultured with MDC-735 compared with control groups. Scale bar, 50 μm ; **(E)** Comparison of the number of phagocytosed glioma cells (Nestin⁺) in individual glioblastoma patient samples after exposure to MDC-735 or control treatments. Data represent means \pm SD; dots represent technical replicates. $n = 4$ to 8 technical replicates per patient sample. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test. For all panels, ns ($P > 0.05$), not significant, $*P < 0.05$, $**P < 0.01$, $***P < 0.001$. Schematic illustration in **(A)** created with BioRender.

Supplementary Materials and Methods

Cell lines

The mouse glioma cell line GL-261 was obtained from the National Cancer Institute, CT-2A cells (#SCC194) were obtained from Merck and SMA-497 as well as SMA-560 were kindly provided by D.D. Bigner (Durham, NC). Human glioma cell lines LN-229 and LN-308 were kindly provided by Professor N. de Tribolet (Lausanne, Switzerland). U-87 MG cell line was obtained from ATCC (HTB-14™) and transduced with EF1a-(Red-Luciferase) lentivirus (#LVP475, Amsbio). These cells were cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM; Thermo Fisher Scientific) supplemented with 10% fetal calf serum (FCS; Thermo Fisher Scientific), 2 mM glutamine (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and 100 U/mL penicillin/100 µg/mL streptomycin solution (Life Technologies). The primary patient-derived glioma initiating cells, ZH-161 and ZH-305 were generated as previously described (48) and maintained in Neurobasal Medium (Gibco) supplemented with 2% B-27 supplement (Gibco), 2 mM glutamine (Gibco), 20 ng/ml epidermal growth factor (PeproTech), 20 ng/ml fibroblast growth factor (FGF) (PeproTech) and 32 international units/ml heparin (Sigma-Aldrich). Sub-cell lines with stable expression of iRFP720 or ZsGreen1 were generated through electroporation using mRNA encoding the Sleeping Beauty transposase SB100X along with the vector pT4, which carries the transgene EF1a-iRFP720-T2A-PuroR-bGHpoly or EF1a-ZsGreen1-T2A-PuroR-bGHpoly (respectively), followed by selection with puromycin (3 µg/ml). Human primary cortical astrocytes (P10251) were obtained from Innoprot (Derio, Spain). They were seeded on flasks coated with 2 µg/cm² poly-L-lysine (PLL; Innoprot) and maintained in complete astrocyte medium (P60101; Innoprot). Human primary corneal epithelial cells (PCS-700-010) were obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (Manassas, VA, USA). They were maintained in complete epithelial medium OcuLife (LL-0032; Lifeline Cell Technology). All cells were cultured in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂ at 37°C. Cell lines were tested and confirmed to be free of mycoplasma contamination using the MycoAlert Mycoplasma Detection Kit (Lonza, LT07-318).

Generation of murine and human macrophages

Mouse bone-marrow-derived macrophages (BMDMs) were differentiated from bone marrow precursors isolated from murine femurs and tibias of C57BL/6 mice as previously described (49). Cells were cultured for 7 days in BMDM growth medium (DMEM/F12 with Glutamax, 10% FBS

and 1% Penicillin/Streptomycin, and 20% L929-conditioned medium) in non-treated petri dishes (Falcon). For human monocyte-derived macrophage generation, PBMCs were collected by peripheral blood draw from healthy donors at the University Hospital Zurich (in accordance with the relevant ethical regulations, BASEC-Nr: 2019-01721) and for large scale by leukapheresis from healthy donors at the Institute of Hematology and Transfusion Medicine in Warsaw. Leukapheresis was performed using the Spectra Optia apheresis system by MTZ Clinical Research Sp. z o.o., with approval from the Bioethical Committee of the Regional Medical Chamber in Warsaw (study no. KB/1359/21). Monocyte isolation was achieved using CD14 microbeads or at large-scale using the CliniMACS Prodigy system (Miltenyi Biotec). Isolated CD14⁺ monocytes were cultured for 7 days in RPMI supplemented with 20% FBS, antibiotics, GlutaMAX, HEPES, and 20 ng/ml of recombinant human M-CSF (170-076-172, Miltenyi Biotec). For human iPSC-derived macrophage differentiation, the human iPSCs line CAAX-RFP (P4) was kindly provided by the Center for Applied Biotechnology (University of Zurich) and maintained in mTeSRTM1 medium on Vitronectin XFTM coated plates. Cells were passaged using ReLeSr passaging reagent. To improve the viability, cells were incubated with ROCK Inhibitor (Y-27632) (Sigma-Aldrich) for the first 24 hours. HiPSCs were harvested for EB formation using TrypLE Express (Gibco). EBs were cultured in mTeSRTM1 medium supplemented with BMP4 (50 ng/ml) (PeproTech), VEGF (50 ng/ml) (PeproTech), SCF (20 ng/ml) (PeproTech), called EB medium and additionally 10 μ M ROCK Inhibitor Y-27632. After 2 weeks, non-adherent monocyte-like precursors were harvested from the supernatant every 3-4 days for up to 6 weeks. They were then seeded in X-VIVO15 media supplemented with M-CSF (100 ng/ml), Glutamax (2mM), 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 mg/ μ L streptomycin and grown for 9-11 days.

Confocal microscopy

To visualize HFt in donor and acceptor cells, macrophages and cancer cells were co-cultured on μ -Slide 8-well chambered coverslips (Ibidi) at a 2:1 ratio (1×10^5 donor and 0.5×10^5 acceptor cells). Ft incubation and CellTrace staining were done as described above and plasma membranes were stained with Alexa Fluor[®] 555-conjugated wheat germ agglutinin (WGA) (Thermo Fisher Scientific) (5 μ g/ml, 10 min at RT). Actin was labeled with phalloidin-iFluor 555 (ab176756, Abcam) or SiR-actin in the presence of Verapamil (#SC001, Spirochrome) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Hoechst 33342 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was used for nuclei staining (concentration: 0.1 μ g/mL-10 μ g/ml). Live-cell imaging or fixation with 4% paraformaldehyde (10 min) was carried out using TCS SP5 (Leica) confocal microscopes with a 63 \times objective. In

time-series experiments, co-cultured cells were allowed to attach for 1 h in the incubator and imaged every 2-3 min for 2 h using an LSM980 (Zeiss) confocal microscope equipped with a climate-control chamber under a 63x objective.

For assessing drug-related microtubule disruption in cancer cells, HMDMs loaded with HFt-735 conjugate were co-cultured with LN-229 cells (labeled with CellTrace) on μ -Slides for 24 h. Cells were then fixed with 4% PFA for 15 min, washed with PBS, and permeabilized and blocked in PBS with 0.1% w/v saponin (Sigma-Aldrich), 0.2% w/v gelatin from cold-water fish skin (Sigma-Aldrich), and 5 mg/ml BSA solution for 15 min. Samples were incubated with primary antibody: anti-beta tubulin (1:100, #ab7751, Abcam) and with secondary antibody: rabbit anti-mouse antibody conjugated with DyLight 650 (1:500; #NBP1-76216, Novus Biologicals). Nuclei were labeled with Hoechst 33342. Imaging was performed using the TCS SP5 (Leica) confocal microscope under a 63x objective.

To visualize HFt transfer within vesicular compartments, HMDMs were first labeled with PKH67 (Sigma Aldrich, #PKH67GL) following the manufacturer's protocol and loaded with HFt-647 as described above. LN-229 cells were stained with CellTrace Violet and then co-cultured with HMDMs on Ibidi slides as previously described. After a 24-hour incubation, the cells were fixed with 4% PFA, washed in PBS, and subsequently permeabilized and blocked for 15 minutes in PBS (Biowest, #L0615) containing 0.1% (w/v) saponin (Sigma-Aldrich, #S7900), 0.2% (w/v) fish skin gelatin (Sigma-Aldrich, #G7765), and 5 mg/mL BSA (Sigma-Aldrich, #A3294). The samples were then incubated with an anti-CD63 primary antibody (1:100, Proteintech #25682-1-AP), diluted in PBS supplemented with 0.1% saponin and 0.2% fish skin gelatin, for 30 minutes at room temperature. Following two washes in the same buffer, a goat anti-rabbit IgG (H+L) secondary antibody conjugated to Alexa Fluor 568 (1:500; Thermo Scientific #A-11036) was applied for an additional 30 minutes at room temperature. Images were acquired on a Leica TCS SP5II confocal microscope equipped with a 63 \times objective, and subsequent image analysis and quantification were performed using ImageJ software.

For staining of ex vivo glioma-bearing mouse brains cryosections from glioma tumor-bearing mice were fixed using 4% PFA for 10 min and permeabilized with PBS containing 0.1% Tween 20 for another 10 minutes, followed by a 30-minute block in SuperBlock solution (Thermo Fisher Scientific). Post-blocking, the samples were incubated with primary antibody rat anti-mouse anti-CD45 conjugated with biotin (#103103, Biolegend) for 1 h at RT. Next, streptavidin conjugated with Alexa Fluor 647 (#405237, Biolegend) was used to detect biotinylated antibody. Nuclei were

labeled with Hoechst 33342. The slides were mounted using a fluorescent mounting medium (Dako), and images were captured using the TCS SP5 (Leica) confocal microscope under a 63x objective. Image analysis was performed using ImageJ software.

Live cell imaging in vitro

Live imaging of HFt transfer and cancer cell killing was performed using the MuviCyte live-cell imaging system by Perkin Elmer. Macrophages, either loaded with HFt conjugates as previously described or left empty as controls, were combined with glioma cells labeled with Violet CellTrace and seeded in a 2:1 ratio (0.2×10^5 macrophages to 0.1×10^5 cancer cells) on 24-well plates. For the cell-killing assay, Incucyte Cytotox Red (Sartorius) was added to the medium at a final concentration of 250 nM. To assess the survival of macrophages loaded with HFt-735, they were labeled with CellTrace. After allowing cells to adhere for 1 hour, they were incubated for up to 72 hours. Fluorescence images were captured at hourly intervals for HFt transfer and every 3 hours for the killing assay. Subsequently, the images were analyzed using Ilastik 1.4, CellProfiler 4.2.1, and ImageJ software to segment CellTrace-dyed cells and quantify cells positive for either HFt-AF488 or Cytotox Red fluorescence. The percentage of dead cells was determined at each time point as the number of Cytotox Red-positive cells divided by the total number of CellTrace-positive cells. The viability was then calculated as the complement of the dead cell percentage and normalized to the initial time point (0 h).

Cytokine profiling

Murine MDC-735 (2×10^6 cells) or PBS (Control) was intratumorally injected into CT-2A tumor-bearing C57BL/6JRj mice on days 5 and 10. Plasma was collected at baseline (day 4), 48 hours after the first treatment (day 7), and 48 hours post-second treatment (day 12). Peripheral blood from the mouse tongue vein was drawn using 0.25 ml EDTA tubes and Microvette capillaries (Sarstedt), following the manufacturer's instructions. Blood samples were centrifuged within 30 minutes of collection; plasma was then transferred to 2 ml cryotubes (Sarstedt), snap-frozen, and stored at -80°C until analysis. Cytokine profiling was conducted using the Immune Monitoring 48-Plex Mouse ProcartaPlex Panel (Thermo Fisher), according to the manufacturer's manual.

Cytokine concentrations in vitro were determined by plating control macrophages, MDC-735, or LN-229 cells at a density of 2×10^4 cells/well in 200 μl of media in a 96-well plate, with each configuration set up in triplicate. For co-culture experiments, 2×10^4 control macrophages or MDC-735 cells were co-seeded with 2×10^4 LN-229 cells in 200 μl of media under identical

conditions. After a 48-hour incubation period, approximately 180 μL of conditioned media was collected from each well and stored at -80°C in a sealed 96-well plate for subsequent analysis. Cytokine profiling was performed using the LEGENDplex Human Essential Immune Response Panel (13-plex), following the manufacturer's protocol. The analysis was conducted using FACSCanto II flow cytometer.

Spectral flow cytometry

CT-2A glioma cells (4×10^4) were stereotactically implanted into the right striatum of C57BL/6JRj mice. On day 7 post-implantation, mice received intratumoral MDC-735 treatment (4 μL) by stereotactic injection, as described above. On day 15, mice were euthanized, and tumor-bearing brain hemispheres, tumor-draining, and non-tumor-draining lymph nodes were harvested. Tissue samples were dissociated as previously described (45). Cell suspensions obtained from the glioma-bearing hemisphere of mouse brains were stained with 100 μL of life-dead Zombie NIR (Biolegend, #423106, 1/800), Fc-Block (anti-CD16/32 Ab, Biolegend, # 101340, 1/200), and anti-mouse CD45.1 biotin antibody and incubated for 20 min at 4°C . Cells were washed and further stained with 100 μL of an antibody mix containing anti-mouse CD49d, CD44, CD19, Ly6G (dilution 1/700), CD4, CX3CR1 BV785, CD88, Ly6C, XCR1, CD64, CD11b, CD204, MHC II, CD8 BV421, CD163, NK1.1 BB700, CD45.2 FITC, TIM-3 PE-Fire810, CD11c, TCR β , PD-L1 PE, CD38, F4/80, and streptavidin BUV395 with Brilliant stain buffer (Invitrogen, # 00-4409-42, 1/8) and incubated for 30 min at 4°C . Cells were washed and permeabilized with 150 μL of Cytofix/Cytoperm (BD Biosciences, # 554714) for 20 min at 4°C . Cells were washed and incubated for 2 h at room temperature with MertK, CD206, and Arginase 1 diluted in Permeabilization buffer (eBioscience, # 00-5523-00, 1X). For the lymphoid panel, cells were stained with 100 μL of life-dead Zombie NIR (Biolegend, #423106, 1/800), Fc-Block (anti-CD16/32 Ab, Biolegend, # 101340, 1/200), and anti-mouse CD103 biotin antibody and incubated for 20 min at 4°C . Cells were washed and further stained with 100 μL of an antibody mix containing anti-mouse CD8 BUV805, CD44 (dilution 1/500), GITR, CD4, TCR $\gamma\delta$, CD69, CD279, ICOS, NK1.1 BV711, CD25, CD62L, CD39 PerCP-eFlour710, CD73, CD45.2 PE-Cy7, TCR β , KLRG1 PE-Dazzle594, CD38, CD27, TIM-3 APC, and streptavidin BB630-P with Brilliant stain buffer (Invitrogen, # 00-4409-42, 1/8) and incubated for 30 min at 4°C . Cells were washed and permeabilized with the Foxp3/transcription factor staining buffer kit (eBioscience, # 00-5523-00) using 150 μL of Fixation/Permeabilization diluted 1/4 into Fixation/Perm diluent and incubating for 35 min at 4°C . Cells were washed and incubated overnight with 100 μL of Permeabilization buffer (eBioscience, # 00-5523-00, 1X)

containing Ki67, Granzyme B, CTLA-4, TCF1, FoxP3 PE-Cy5.5, and TOX antibodies. On the morning after, cells were washed, resuspended in 100 μ L of PBS, and acquired using a Cytex Aurora 5L - Spectral Analyzer.

The tumor-draining lymph node and non-tumor-draining lymph node cell suspensions were stained with 100 μ L of life-dead Zombie NIR (Biolegend, #423106, 1/800), Fc-Block (anti-CD16/32 Ab, Biolegend, # 101340, 1/200) and incubated for 20 min at 4°C. Cells were washed and further stained with 50 μ L of an antibody mix containing CXCR5, CXCR3, and CX3CR1 PE-Dazzle 594 and incubated at 37°C for 15 min. Cells were placed on ice and further stained with 50 μ L of anti-mouse CD8 BUV805, CD44, CD19, Ly6G, CD4, CD45, PDL1 Superbright 780, ICOS, Ly6C, XCR1, PD-1, CD62L, CD11b, MHC-II, Sirp α , CD11c, TCR β , KLRG1 APC-Cy7, CD39 AF647, CD301b, and streptavidin BV421 with Brilliant stain buffer (Invitrogen, # 00-4409-42, 1/8) and incubated for 30 min at 4°C. For this purpose, antibodies were prepared at two times the concentration to reach the proper final concentration. Cells were washed and permeabilized with the Foxp3/transcription factor staining buffer kit (eBioscience, # 00-5523-00) using 150 μ L of Fixation/Permeabilization diluted 1/4 into Fixation/Perm diluent and incubating for 35 min at 4°C. Cells were washed and incubated overnight with 100 μ L of Permeabilization buffer (eBioscience, # 00-5523-00, 1X) containing TCF-1 and FOXP3 PE antibodies. On the morning after, cells were washed, resuspended in 100 μ L of PBS, and acquired using a Cytex Aurora 5L - Spectral Analyzer. For all staining more information about the antibodies used and their dilutions are available in the supplementary material (Supplementary Table 2) if not stated differently in the text. Data were acquired on a 5L Cytex Aurora (Cytex), and raw fcs-files were preprocessed using FlowJo. Compensated and pregated cells were imported into RStudio using R (version 4.0/4.2.2) and the flowCore package. After hyperbolic arcsine (arcsinh) transformation and percentile normalization, dimensionally reduced data was plotted in UMAP by applying the umap package in R. Automated clustering and metaclustering were performed with the FlowSOM algorithm followed by expert-guided corrections.

Proteomics

BMDM were loaded with biotinylated ferritin or non-labeled ferritin as control. Then co-cultured with CT-2A glioma cancer cells for 24h and separated by CD11b magnetic beads. Subsequently, the samples were lysed and incubated with streptavidin beads according to the online protocol (50), followed by on-bead digestion and liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS) analysis by data-dependent acquisition (DDA) on an Orbitrap Lumos Tribrid (Thermo Fisher Scientific) LUMOS mass spectrometer. Proteins identified in samples containing unlabeled ferritin were

considered as "unspecific background" and were removed from the corresponding Mascot search results (Matrix Science. Parameters; Trypsin/P, no missed cleavages, Uniport human and mouse database plus common contaminations. Fix modification: Carbamidomethyl (C) - variable Acetyl (Protein Nterm), Deamidation (NQ) and Oxidation (M)) obtained from affinity purification (AP-MS) experiments with biotinylated ferritin. Pre-filtered protein (FDR<1%, 2 peptides per protein) matrices were imported in RStudio (v2021.09.0+351.pro6) and human contaminants were removed. Gene symbols from raw output were mapped to Entrez IDs using the AnnotationDbi::select() function (AnnotationDbi package version 3.12) and unmapped genes were manually curated using Genbank (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>). Enrichment analysis was performed using the clusterProfiler::enrichGO function (clusterProfiler package version 3.18) with the full murine background (org.Mm.eg.db version 3.8.2). GO biological processes were searched for gene sets of 50-150 proteins (p adj. cutoff 0.05/q value cutoff 0.05).

mRNA generation and electroporation

The mRNAs encoding for the murine CCR2 (NCBI Gene ID: 12772) were generated by in vitro transcription at the mRNA platform of University Hospital Zurich as previously described (51). The functionality was confirmed by transfection of RAW264.7 or BMDM and subsequent detection of the respective protein by flow cytometry. For electroporation using the Maxcyte GTX, RAW264.7 or BMDMs were counted before electroporation and washed once in Electroporation Buffer (Maxcyte) and resuspended at 2×10^8 /ml for the electroporation with mRNA encoding the CCR2 using 1 μ g mRNA per million cells. 10×10^6 RAW264.7 or BMDMs were resuspended in 50 μ l and respective amounts of mRNA were added. Cells were then transferred into R50 \times 3 processing assemblies and electroporated using the RAW264.7 or HSC-3 protocol for electroporation. Post electroporation cells were rested in electroporation buffer for 30 min.

siRNA gene knockdown

Cells were transfected with siRNA using Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific) following the manufacturer's optimized protocol for LN-229. Predesigned Silencer Select siRNAs targeting CTSB (siCTSB-3738, ID: s3738 and siCTSB-3739, ID: s3739; Invitrogen) and a non-targeting negative control siRNA no. 1 (Invitrogen, #4390843) were used. After transfection, cells were incubated at 37°C in a humidified 5% CO₂ atmosphere for the optimized duration before downstream analyses.

To confirm knockdown efficiency, Western Blot analysis was performed. Cells were lysed in RIPA buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #89900) supplemented with Halt Protease and Phosphatase Inhibitor Cocktail (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #78440). Lysates were cleared by centrifugation at $16,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C. Total protein concentration was determined using the Pierce BCA Protein Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #23225). Protein samples (20 µg) were prepared by mixing with NuPAGE LDS Sample Buffer (4X) (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #NP0007) and NuPAGE Sample Reducing Agent (10X) (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #NP0009), then heated at 70°C for 10 min. Proteins were resolved on a NuPAGE 4–12% Bis-Tris Gel (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #NP0321BOX) using NuPAGE MOPS SDS Running Buffer (20X) (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #NP0001) and transferred onto a 0.45 µm nitrocellulose membrane (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #88025) using NuPAGE Transfer Buffer (20X) (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #NP0006). Membranes were blocked in 5% (w/v) non-fat dry milk in TBS-T (Tris-buffered saline with 0.05% Tween 20; Sigma-Aldrich; #PPB002-20PAK) for 60 min at room temperature, then incubated overnight at 4°C with primary antibodies: anti-Cathepsin B (D1C7Y) XP Rabbit mAb (Cell Signaling Technology; #31718) and anti- α -tubulin antibody (Cell Signaling Technology; #3873T) in 2.5% (w/v) non-fat dry milk in TBS-T. After three washes in TBS-T, membranes were incubated for 1 h at room temperature with HRP-conjugated secondary antibodies (anti-rabbit IgG, HRP-linked antibody, Cell Signaling Technology; #7074, or anti-mouse IgG, HRP-linked antibody, Cell Signaling Technology; #7076) at 1:10,000 dilution in 2.5% (w/v) non-fat dry milk in TBS-T, then washed three times in TBS-T. Proteins were visualized using ECL Western blotting substrate (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #32106) and an iBright 1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific; #A44126).

CRISPR/Cas9 gene knockout

Gene knockout was performed with Cas9/sgRNA-ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complex using the Neon device (Invitrogen). For each target gene, two distinct pre-designed sgRNAs (Integrated DNA Technologies) were used to create short deletions (sequence-PAM; Stab1: GCGACACCGTGTAGTGGCCA-CGG, AGTCAGGCCCAAATCTGTTG-GGG). Control cells were processed identically but were electroporated with scrambled controls (Integrated DNA Technologies). Deletion was tested using PCR with primers flanking targeted sequence (forward 5'-CTCAACCTTCTTCAACCAGTGA-3'; reverse 5'-TCTGAGACTCCCATATGCAAAA-3'). Bulk-electroporated or single-cell-derived clones were used in experiments as specified in figure legend.

Imaging flow cytometry

To evaluate changes in actin cytoskeleton organization during macrophage–tumor cell interactions, human monocyte-derived macrophages (HMDMs) loaded with HFt-AF488 (as described above) were co-cultured with LN-229 cells pre-labeled with CellTrace Violet. The co-culture was performed in 5 mL polystyrene tubes (Falcon, #352054) at a 2:1 ratio (8×10^5 HMDMs and 4×10^5 cancer cells) in a 1 mL volume of RPMI medium (Sigma-Aldrich, #R8758) supplemented with 10% FBS (HyClone, #SV30160.03) and 20 ng/mL M-CSF (BioLegend, #574808). After a 2-hour incubation, cells were fixed by slowly adding 1.5 mL of 2% PFA (Thermo Scientific, #28908) during gently vortexing. Following 10 minutes at room temperature, fixation was halted by adding 1.5 mL PBS (Biowest, #L0615) containing 1% BSA (AppliChem, #A1391). The cells were then pelleted ($300 \times g$ for 8 minutes, RT).

To visualize filamentous actin (F-actin), cells were permeabilized (PBS + 1% BSA + 0.1% saponin) and stained with iFluor 555–conjugated phalloidin (Abcam, #ab176756). Post-staining, cells were washed in PBS (Biowest, #L0615), spun down ($250 \times g$, 5 minutes), and gently resuspended in PBS at a final concentration of $1\text{--}5 \times 10^7$ cells/mL. Samples were analyzed on an ImageStreamX Mark II (Amnis) imaging flow cytometer (Flow Cytometry Facility, University of Zurich). Appropriate gating strategies were used to identify macrophage–tumor cell doublets that were in focus and positive for the respective fluorescence markers. Acquired images were processed using IDEAS 6.2 (Amnis), and subsequent fluorescence intensity analyses were conducted with ImageJ.

Fig. S1. Characterization of ferritin-conjugate transfer in vitro. (A) Flow cytometry analysis of HFt-AF488 transfer from loaded hiPSC-DMs to human glioma cell lines. Representative density plots (left), bar plots illustrating the average geometric mean fluorescence intensity (geo-MFI) (middle), and the percentage of AF488-positive cells (right). Data are presented as mean \pm SD from $n = 3$ independent replicates. Dots represent individual sample replicates. (B and C) Representative confocal microscopy images showing HFt-AF488 transfer to (B) LN-229 or (C) ZH-161 human glioma cells in co-culture with hiPSC-DMs. Scale bars, 20 μm ; inset, 5 μm . (D) Time-lapse microscopy quantification of HFt-AF488 transfer from HMDMs to LN-229 or ZH-161 glioma cells. Data are presented as mean \pm SD from $n=3$ independent replicates based on two representative fields of view. (E) Mass spectrometry spectra of HFt-735 conjugates illustrating single-/double-labeled HFt-735 conjugates and free protein for drug-fraction determination. (F) LC-MS chromatograms of free MMAE (top) and HFt-735 conjugate (bottom). The area of free MMAE peak was used to determine the concentration of free drug. (G) HPLC-MS analysis of MMAE loading in macrophages. Bars represent mean \pm SD ($n = 10$ independent BMDM samples; $n = 22$ independent HMDM samples). Dots represent individual sample replicates. (H) Western blot confirming cathepsin B knockdown and (I) viability of LN-229 glioma cells after 48-hour co-culture with HFt-735-loaded HMDMs (MDC-735). Cells were either untreated (Control), transfected with non-targeting siRNA (siScr Control), or transfected with siRNAs targeting cathepsin B (siCTSB-3738 and siCTSB-3739). Viability is expressed as the number of live LN-229 cells relative to the siScr Control. Bars represent mean \pm SD from $n = 2$ independent replicates. Dots represent individual sample replicates. (J) Confocal images showing multinucleated LN-229 cells following 24-hour co-culture with MDC-735. Scale bar, 10 μm . (K) Representative confocal images of HMDMs loaded with HFt-735-AF488 double conjugate, demonstrating co-localization of MMAE with HFt inside the macrophages using anti-MMAE antibody staining. Scale bar, 20 μm ; inset, 5 μm . (L) LN-229 glioma cell viability (number of live cancer cells relative to control) following co-culture with plain HMDMs (Control), HMDMs loaded with HFt-AF488 or HMDMs loaded with HFt-735 for 72 hours, assessed by flow cytometry. Bars represent mean \pm SD from $n = 3$ technical replicates. (M) Quantification of phagocytosis by imaging flow cytometry. Bars represent mean \pm SD from $n = 3$ independent replicates. Dots represent individual sample replicates. (N) Representative imaging flow cytometry images depicting fluorescently labeled murine MDC-735, CT-2A-zsGreen, and MDC-735 indicating phagocytosis events quantified in (M). (O) Time-lapse fluorescence microscopy showing CT-2A-zsGreen phagocytosis by murine MDC-735 (BMDMs) across 48 hours. Representative images from selected time-points are shown. Scale bar, 100 μm . Statistical analysis was performed using a paired two-tailed t-test in (A), one-way ANOVA with Tukey's post hoc test in (I) and (L), and a Student's t-test in (G) and (M). For all panels, ns, not significant, $*$ $P \leq 0.05$, $**P \leq 0.01$, $***P \leq 0.001$.

Fig. S2. Comparative anti-cancer efficacy of macrophages loaded with HFt-735, BSA-735, or free drug. (A-B) Flow cytometry analysis of glioma cell viability after co-culture with macrophages loaded with BSA-735 or HFt-735. **(A)** CT-2A glioma cell viability from 24 to 72 hours after co-culture with BMDMs loaded with varying concentrations of BSA-735 or HFt-735 ($n = 3$ technical replicates). **(B)** LN-229 glioma cell viability in monoculture or after 48-hour co-culture with plain HMDMs, HMDMs loaded with BSA-735 (HMDM-BSA-735), or HMDMs loaded with HFt-735 (MDC-735) at $1 \mu\text{M}$ ($n = 3$ independent replicates). Dots represent individual sample replicates. **(A-B)** Data are shown as the number of viable cells relative to the control condition. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test. For all panels, ns, not significant, $*P < 0.05$, $**P < 0.01$, $***P < 0.001$, $****P < 0.0001$.

Fig. S3. In vivo biodistribution and phenotypic characterization of MDC-735. (A-B) Fluorescence Molecular Tomography (FMT) images showing HfT-AF790 fluorescence in glioma tumors following intratumoral (IT) and intravenous (IV) administration of free HfT-AF790 or BMDM-HfT-AF790. (C) Quantitative comparison of AF790 fluorescence intensity derived from FMT imaging, contrasting IT versus IV delivery methods. Data are presented as mean \pm SD from $n = 3$ mice per group. Dots represent individual sample replicates. (D) Flow cytometry analysis of dissociated tumor-bearing brains 24 hours after intratumoral injection of BMDM-HfT-AF488 or control. Left: Scatter plots illustrating HfT-AF488 signal in iRFP720+ cancer cells. Middle: Bar plots showing the geo-MFI of AF488. Right: Bar plots representing the percentage of AF488+ iRFP720+ cells. Data are presented as mean \pm SD from $n = 3$ mice samples. Dots represent individual sample replicates. (E - F) Flow cytometry analysis of marker expression in human monocytes, macrophages, and MDC-735. (E) Box plot comparisons of the percentage of cells positive for specific markers. (F) Median fluorescence intensity (MFI) of marker expression in monocytes, macrophages, and MDC-735 following cryopreservation and thawing (analyzed 24 hours post-thaw). Data from $n = 3$ leukopak donors. Dots represent individual sample replicates. (G) Flow cytometry analysis of live LN-229 glioma cells following 72- hour co-culture with MDC-735, M2-like macrophages, and M0-like macrophages at a 1:1:1 ratio (effector-to-target-to-macrophage). Data represent mean \pm SD from $n = 3$ independent replicates. Dots represent individual sample replicates. (H) Time-lapse IncuCyte S3 of LN-229-GFP fluorescence measurement in co-culture with MDC-735, M2-like macrophages and M0-like macrophages at a 1:1:1 ratio (E:T:MF). Data represent mean \pm SD from $n = 3$ technical replicates. Statistical analysis was performed using a one-way ANOVA with Tukey HSD post hoc test in (C, E–G), and a Student's t-test in (D). For all panels, ns, not significant, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$.

Fig. S4. Fluorescence distribution and tumor size analysis in an organotypic CT-2A-zsGreen glioblastoma brain slice model. (A) Schematic of the treatment schedule. Created with BioRender.com. (B-C) Representative confocal microscopy images illustrating BMDMs, HFt and MMAE distribution following intra-slice injection of BMDM-HFt-735 (MDC-735) or the control mixture (BMDMs, HFt, and MMAE) within organotypic CT-2A-zsGreen glioblastoma brain slices at 24 hours (B) and 48 hours (C). Scale bars, 200 μm ; insets, 100 μm . (D) Magnified tumor cross-section after injecting a mixture of BMDMs, free HFt and MMAE. Scale bar, 50 μm . (E) Tumor perimeter 48 hours post-injection. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 5$ independent slices for MDC-735; $n = 6$ independent slices for the control mixture). Dots represent individual sample replicates. Statistical analysis: Student's t-test. ** $P < 0.01$.

Fig. S5. Dose-dependent therapeutic response to MDC-735 in CT-2A glioma-bearing mice. (A) Schematic of the treatment schedule. Created with BioRender.com. **(B)** MRI images showing CT-2A glioma tumors in PBS control mice and mice treated with 2×10^6 MDC-735, with tumor boundaries

outlined. **(C)** Tumor area from MRI images shown in **(B)**. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$ mice per group). Dots represent individual sample replicates. Statistical analysis: Student's t -test. $*P < 0.05$. **(D)** Kaplan-Meier survival curves of CT-2A glioma-bearing mice following intratumoral (IT) administration of MDC-735 at different doses ($n = 6$ mice per group). **(E)** Table summarizing median survival times (days) of treated mice. **(F)** Schematic of the treatment schedule and **(G)** Kaplan-Meier survival curves of CT-2A glioma tumor-bearing C57BL/6 mice following intratumoral (IT) administration of BMDMs loaded with BSA-735, BMDMs incubated with free unconjugated drug (BMDM+735) at equimolar concentrations to HfT-735; or PBS control ($n = 6$ mice per group). Survival analyzes were performed using the log-rank test, $**P < 0.01$.

Fig. S6. Tumor imaging and safety assessment of MDC-735 treatment. (A) Time-course FMT imaging of ZH-161-iRFP720 tumor fluorescence across treatment groups. (B) Tumor fluorescence over time. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 6$ mice per group). Dots represent individual sample replicates. (C) Plasma concentrations of anti-drug antibody (ADA) in healthy mice after intracranial injection of MDC-735 or PBS control. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 6$ mice per group). Dots represent individual sample replicates. (D) Hematology and serum chemistry measurements in healthy mice following intracranial administration of MDC-735 versus PBS control. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 6$ mice per group). Dots represent individual sample replicates. Grey area represents normal concentrations for each parameter. (B-D) Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with Tukey HSD post hoc test. For all panels, ns, not significant, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Fig. S7. Histological safety evaluation of organ tissues following MDC-735 treatment. Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and CD68 staining of (A) brain tumor tissue from human glioma-bearing mice treated with MDC-735, (B) liver sections, (C) kidney sections, (D) lung sections. Images are shown at Day 7 and 28 post-treatment, comparing effects of MDC-735 to PBS control. Scale bars, 350 μm .

Fig. S8. Histological safety evaluation of organ tissues following MDC-735 treatment. Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and CD68 staining of (A) spleen sections, (B) heart sections, (C) stomach sections, (D) ovary sections. Images are shown at Day 7 and 28 post-treatment, comparing effects of MDC-735 to PBS control. Scale bars, 350 μm .

Fig. S9. Histological safety evaluation of organ tissues following MDC-735 treatment. Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and CD68 staining of (A) skin sections, (B) small intestine section, (C) large intestine sections, and (D) testicle sections. Images are shown at Day 7 and 28 post-treatment, comparing effects of MDC-735 to PBS control. Scale bars, 350 μm.

Fig. S10. Analysis of tumor microenvironment (TME) following MDC-735 treatment and depletion studies. (A) Representative UMAP plots showing marker gene expression within each cell cluster from dissociated tumor-bearing brain hemisphere spectral flow cytometry analysis. (B-C) Gating strategy for selected immune cell populations. (D) Box plot of the proportion of regulatory T cells (Treg) within the non-tumor draining lymph nodes (Non TDLN) (n = 2-5). Dots represent individual sample replicates. (E) Representative combined density scatter plot and box plot showing the expression of CD39 and PD1 on Tregs within non TDLN (n = 2-5). (F) Representative scatter plot detailing the gating of injected CD45.1⁺ macrophages versus host CD45.2⁺ cell populations, comparing empty macrophages (BMDMs) and MDC-735. (G) Box plot of the frequency of injected empty BMDMs and MDC-735 in dissociated tumor-bearing brain samples (n = 4-5). Dots represent individual sample replicates. (H) Representative density plots comparing the phenotype of empty BMDMs and MDC-735 based on selected macrophage markers. (I) Bar plots comparing selected macrophage marker expression between empty BMDMs and MDC-735 in TME (n = 4-5). Dots represent individual sample replicates. (J) Representative scatter plots showing flow cytometry confirmation of in vivo CD4 and CD8 lymphocyte depletion using depleting antibodies. (K) Kaplan-Meier survival curves illustrating the therapeutic efficacy of IT administered MDC-735 in immunocompetent mice versus mice with CD4 and CD8 depleted lymphocytes, with PBS used as a control treatment (n = 7 mice per group). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with post-hoc Tukey HSD test for (D), (E), Student's t-test for (G), (H), and (I), and log-rank test for (K). For all panels, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

Fig. S11. FMT in vivo imaging of fluorescently labeled macrophages and tumor signal of GL-261 glioma-bearing mice treated with or without local pre-irradiation. (A) Representative FMT images showing CellBrite-790-labeled macrophages. (B) Representative FMT images displaying the iRFP720 tumor signal at selected time points. (C) FMT signal quantification of iRFP720 tumor fluorescence (n = 6 mice per group). Dots represent individual sample replicates. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with post hoc Tukey HSD test. Only the most relevant statistical comparisons are depicted. For all panels, ns, not significant, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

Fig. S12. FMT in vivo imaging of fluorescently labeled macrophages or CCR2-overexpressing macrophages and tumor signal in GL-261 glioma-bearing mice. (A) Representative FMT images illustrating CellBrite-790-labeled macrophage fluorescence at different timepoints. (B) Representative FMT images showing the iRFP720 tumor signal at selected time points.

Fig. S13. The transfer of ferritin from macrophages to glioma cells depends on cell-cell contacts and involves rearrangements of cytoskeleton and vesicle transfer. (A) Time-series confocal images illustrating the establishment of direct cell-cell contact between HMDM and LN-229 glioma cells. Scale bar, 10 μm ; inset, 5 μm . (B) Time-series confocal images showing HFt-AF488 transfer to LN-229 cells (arrowheads), appearing upon contact with HMDM-HFt-AF488. Scale bar, 10 μm ; inset 5 μm . (C) Venn diagram showing the number of potential HFt-binding proteins identified by AP-MS in BMDM and glioma cells and in control BMDM incubated without glioma cells. (D) Pathway enrichment analysis of biological processes mapped by HFt-binding proteins detected in BMDM loaded with biotinylated HFt after co-culture with glioma cells. Analysis was conducted using the clusterProfiler R package and p-values were adjusted for multiple comparisons using the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure. (E) PCR validation of stabilin-1 knockout in RAW264.7 cells or CT-2A glioma cells. (F) Flow-cytometry quantification of HFt-AF488 uptake in wildtype (NC) or stabilin-1 knockout (KO) RAW264.7 cells. Bar plots represent mean \pm SD from $n = 3$ independent replicates. Dots represent individual sample replicates. Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test. (G) Flow cytometry analysis of HFt-AF488 transfer to glioma cells in co-cultures of wildtype or stabilin-1 knockout RAW264.7 cells with wildtype or stabilin-1 knockout CT-2A glioma cells. Bar plots represent mean \pm SD from $n = 3$ independent replicates. Dots represent individual sample replicates. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with post hoc Tukey HSD test. For all panels, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

Fig S14. HfT transfer and phagocytosis efficiency in co-cultures of MDC-735 with dissociated glioblastoma-tumor samples from human patients. (A) HfT-AF647 transfer from macrophages to tumor vs. non-tumor cells in surgically obtained glioblastoma samples. Bar plots represent mean \pm SD from $n = 10$ independent samples. Dots represent individual sample replicates. Student's t-test was used for statistical analysis. (B) The ratio of ferritin transfer to tumor cells versus non-tumor cells for each individual patient (dots represent $n = 4$ technical replicates) (C). The number of phagocytosed glioma cells (Nestin+) in glioblastoma patient samples, following exposure to MDC-735 or control treatments. Bar plots represent mean \pm SD from $n = 10$ independent samples. Dots represent individual sample replicates. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with post hoc Tukey HSD test. For all panels, * $P < 0.05$, *** $P < 0.001$.

Table S1. Murine study hematologic and serum biochemistry parameter analysis for safety profile.Data represent mean \pm SD from n = 6 mice per group.

PBS Control Group i.t.treatment				
Parameter	Day 7 (mean\pmsd)	Day 28 (mean\pmsd)	Units	Normal range
Blood cell counts				
RBC	7.94 \pm 2.41	10.13 \pm 0.9	10 ¹² /L	[6.0–10.26]
HCT	42.9 \pm 13.27	54.98 \pm 4.83	%	[36.85–50.71]
HGB	12.8 \pm 4.15	16.7 \pm 1.66	g/dL	[11.62–15.64]
MCV	53.9 \pm 1.55	54.33 \pm 0.95	fL	[45.44–66.92]
MCH	15.9 \pm 0.81	16.5 \pm 0.23	pg	[13.98–21.12]
MCHC	29.6 \pm 1.21	30.35 \pm 0.70	g/dL	[29.71–32.73]
RDW	15.1 \pm 0.79	15.07 \pm 1.49	%	
RDW-SD	32.1 \pm 1.48	31.27 \pm 3.05	fL	
WBC	2.26 \pm 1.04	2.31 \pm 2.91	10 ⁹ /L	
Neutrophiles	1.03 \pm 0.98	0.44 \pm 0.40	10 ⁹ /L	
Lymphocytes	1.11 \pm 1.23	1.87 \pm 3.20	10 ⁹ /L	
Monocytes	0 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	10 ⁹ /L	
Eosinophiles	0 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	10 ⁹ /L	
Basophiles	0 \pm 0	0 \pm 0	10 ⁹ /L	
PLT	595 \pm 278	527 \pm 117	10 ⁹ /L	[306–1044]
PDW	6.65 \pm 0.75	12.2 \pm 4.3	fL	
MPV	6.7 \pm 0.5	8.1 \pm 1.3	fL	[5.69–8.99]
PCT	0.39 \pm 0.18	0.4 \pm 0.1	%	
Biochemistry parameter				
GLU	18.28 \pm 4.3	20.20 \pm 11.53	mmol/L	
CREA	62.01 \pm 30.74	121.15 \pm 116.17	μ mol/L	[17–81]
Urea	6.04 \pm 0.80	9.93 \pm 4.25	mmol/L	[5.36–13.92]
Bun:Cre	24 \pm 13	29 \pm 16		
PHOS	2.99 \pm 0.28	4.14 \pm 0.71	mmol/L	[1.71–3.64]
Calcium	2.59 \pm 0.20	2.70 \pm 0.23	mmol/L	[1.47–2.96]
Sodium	173.35 \pm 8.00	257.52 \pm 109.45	mmol/L	[145–174]
Potassium	7.88 \pm 0.89	9.95 \pm 3.05	mmol/L	[6.5–10.5]
Na:K	22 \pm 3	26 \pm 5		
T-Protein	61.49 \pm 6.46	64.88 \pm 9.65	g/L	[33–76]
Albumin	27.4 \pm 1.5	26.67 \pm 4.05	g/L	[26–54]
Globulin	34.1 \pm 7.5	36.11 \pm 12.63	g/L	[20–38]
ALB:GLOB	0.8 \pm 0.2	0.75 \pm 0.23		[14–140]
ALT	31.27 \pm 5.35	40.26 \pm 16.19	U/L	[14–140]
ALP	67.5 \pm 8.63	62.44 \pm 25.82	U/L	[46–291]
AMYL	1200.31 \pm 135.61	1656.92 \pm 633.66	U/L	[200–2500]
T-Bilirubin	5.63 \pm 1.90	10.11 \pm 6.40	μ mol/L	[1.71–15.39]
CHOL	4.02 \pm 0.54	4.05 \pm 1.58	mmol/L	[0.9–5.66]
TBA	1.39 \pm 0.73	2.33 \pm 0.98	μ mol/L	[0–15]

MDC-735 Group i.t. treatment				
Parameter	Day 7 (mean±sd)	Day 28 (mean±sd)	Units	Normal range
Blood cell counts				
RBC	7.89 ± 1.96	9.26 ± 0.74	10 ¹² /L	[6.0–10.26]
HCT	42.62 ± 11.32	49.62 ± 4.93	%	[36.85–50.71]
HGB	12.85 ± 3.38	15.17 ± 1.14	g/dL	[11.62–15.64]
MCV	53.68 ± 2.24	53.53 ± 1.41	fL	[45.44–66.92]
MCH	16.23 ± 0.54	16.4 ± 0.37	pg	[13.98–21.12]
MCHC	30.27 ± 0.75	30.65 ± 1.2	g/dL	[29.71–32.73]
RDW	14.95 ± 0.67	14.85 ± 0.18	%	
RDW-SD	31.77 ± 2.25	30.83 ± 0.85	fL	
WBC	1.71 ± 0.7	1.01 ± 0.28	10 ⁹ /L	
Neutrophils	1.23 ± 0.91	0.21 ± 0.21	10 ⁹ /L	
Lymphocytes	0.48 ± 0.69	0.76 ± 0.31	10 ⁹ /L	
Monocytes	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	10 ⁹ /L	
Eosinophils	0 ± 0	0.03 ± 0.07	10 ⁹ /L	
Basophils	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	10 ⁹ /L	
PLT	588.5 ± 166.89	473.5 ± 133.1	10 ⁹ /L	[306–1044]
PDW	7.3 ± 1.03	11.8 ± 4.3	fL	
MPV	6.6 ± 0.52	7.78 ± 0.84	fL	[5.69–8.99]
PCT	0.39 ± 0.11	0.36 ± 0.08	%	
Biochemistry parameter				
GLU	16.34 ± 1.78	18.04 ± 5.64	mmol/L	
CREA	84 ± 12.85	115.83 ± 42.34	μmol/L	[17–81]
Urea	6.29 ± 0.61	7.75 ± 1.03	mmol/L	[5.36–13.92]
Bun:Cre	18.83 ± 2.23	19.17 ± 9.66		
PHOS	3.56 ± 0.24	3.56 ± 0.37	mmol/L	[1.71–3.64]
Calcium	2.49 ± 0.16	2.35 ± 0.33	mmol/L	[1.47–2.96]
Sodium	172 ± 6.78	200.33 ± 27.4	mmol/L	[145–174]
Potassium	7.34 ± 1.81	8.79 ± 0.89	mmol/L	[6.5–10.5]
Na:K	21.33 ± 0.82	22.67 ± 1.75		
T-Protein	56.83 ± 2.79	63.5 ± 7.77	g/L	[33–76]
Albumin	28.17 ± 1.83	28 ± 1.26	g/L	[26–54]
Globulin	28.67 ± 2.58	35.67 ± 7.34	g/L	[20–38]
ALB:GLOG	1 ± 0	1 ± 0		
ALT	33.5 ± 4.32	42.33 ± 9.31	U/L	[14–140]
ALP	62.17 ± 12.43	61.5 ± 8.26	U/L	[46–291]
AMYL	1104.17 ± 101.44	1152.33 ± 149.42	U/L	[200–2500]
T-Bilirubin	5.83 ± 1.95	6.81 ± 3.28	μmol/L	[1.71–15.39]
CHOL	4.37 ± 0.7	4.79 ± 1.16	mmol/L	[0.9–5.66]
TBA	1.46 ± 1.23	1.16 ± 0.8	μmol/L	[0–15]

PBS Control Group i.c.treatment				
Parameter	Day 7 (mean±sd)	Day 28 (mean±sd)	Units	Normal range
Blood cell counts				
RBC	7.91 ± 1.62	9.13 ± 0.38	10 ¹² /L	[6.0–10.26]
HCT	43.2 ± 8.87	49.7 ± 3.64	%	[36.85–50.71]
HGB	13.05 ± 2.76	15.05 ± 0.56	g/dL	[11.62–15.64]
MCV	54.58 ± 0.71	54.55 ± 2.10	fL	[45.44–66.92]
MCH	16.47 ± 0.43	16.52 ± 0.22	pg	[13.98–21.12]
MCHC	30.17 ± 0.52	30.38 ± 1.22	g/dL	[29.71–32.73]
RDW	15.1 ± 0.56	14.63 ± 0.24	%	
RDW-SD	32.65 ± 0.89	30.98 ± 0.96	fL	
WBC	1.89 ± 0.97	1.00 ± 0.17	10 ⁹ /L	
Neutrophils	0.37 ± 0.63	0.64 ± 0.26	10 ⁹ /L	
Lymphocytes	1.52 ± 1.18	0.26 ± 0.35	10 ⁹ /L	
Monocytes	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	10 ⁹ /L	
Eosinophils	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	10 ⁹ /L	
Basophils	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	10 ⁹ /L	
PLT	581 ± 113	607 ± 82	10 ⁹ /L	[306–1044]
PDW	9.0 ± 4.2	8.8 ± 1.7	fL	
MPV	6.7 ± 0.5	7.0 ± 0.2	fL	[5.69–8.99]
PCT	0.39 ± 0.08	0.43 ± 0.06	%	
Biochemistry parameter				
GLU	14.47 ± 3.65	19.29 ± 3.68	mmol/L	
CREA	52.52 ± 19.47	44.8 ± 10.17	μmol/L	[17–81]
Urea	6.55 ± 0.74	7.61 ± 1.18	mmol/L	[5.36–13.92]
Bun:Cre	17 ± 4.55	28 ± 17		
PHOS	3.45 ± 0.16	3.32 ± 0.24	mmol/L	[1.71–3.64]
Calcium	2.45 ± 0.14	2.55 ± 0.16	mmol/L	[1.47–2.96]
Sodium	169.71 ± 24.24	163.76 ± 7.92	mmol/L	[145–174]
Potassium	7.74 ± 0.62	8.53 ± 0.61	mmol/L	[6.5–10.5]
Na:K	23 ± 3	21 ± 2		
T-Protein	57.34 ± 2.07	56.94 ± 1.49	g/L	[33–76]
Albumin	26.13 ± 3.88	26.95 ± 1.68	g/L	[26–54]
Globulin	31.21 ± 4.70	29.99 ± 1.80	g/L	[20–38]
ALB:GLOB	1.12 ± 0.44	0.90 ± 0.1		[14–140]
ALT	35.50 ± 5.62	42.96 ± 14.77	U/L	[14–140]
ALP	75.26 ± 12.28	67.54 ± 6.15	U/L	[46–291]
AMYL	1046.30 ± 136.16	1058.66 ± 73.36	U/L	[200–2500]
T-Bilirubin	7.17 ± 3.48	5.09 ± 3.03	μmol/L	[1.71–15.39]
CHOL	4.20 ± 0.82	4.12 ± 0.45	mmol/L	[0.9–5.66]
TBA	1.93 ± 0.94	1.20 ± 1.11	μmol/L	[0–15]

MDC-735 Group i.c. treatment				
Parameter	Day 7 (mean±sd)	Day 28 (mean±sd)	Units	Normal range
Blood cell counts				
RBC	8.68 ± 1.13	8.95 ± 0.24	10 ¹² /L	[6.0–10.26]
HCT	48.37 ± 6.70	48.98 ± 1.28	%	[36.85–50.71]
HGB	14.30 ± 2.10	14.85 ± 0.23	g/dL	[11.62–15.64]
MCV	55.70 ± 1.41	54.78 ± 1.85	fL	[45.44–66.92]
MCH	16.43 ± 0.55	16.6 ± 0.29	pg	[13.98–21.12]
MCHC	29.53 ± 0.84	30.37 ± 0.60	g/dL	[29.71–32.73]
RDW	15.15 ± 0.27	14.75 ± 0.41	%	
RDW-SD	33.08 ± 1.40	31.35 ± 1.53	fL	
WBC	1.66 ± 0.46	1.09 ± 0.20	10 ⁹ /L	
Neutrophils	0.915 ± 0.35	0.42 ± 0.43	10 ⁹ /L	
Lymphocytes	0.53 ± 0.57	0.66 ± 0.45	10 ⁹ /L	
Monocytes	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	10 ⁹ /L	
Eosinophils	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	10 ⁹ /L	
Basophils	0 ± 0	0 ± 0	10 ⁹ /L	
PLT	639 ± 89	591 ± 19	10 ⁹ /L	[306–1044]
PDW	8.5 ± 4.5	9 ± 1.6	fL	
MPV	6.6 ± 0.5	7.1 ± 0.2	fL	[5.69–8.99]
PCT	0.42 ± 0.1	0.42 ± 0.02	%	
Biochemistry parameter				
GLU	19.30 ± 1.97	15.76 ± 1.83	mmol/L	
CREA	83.84 ± 38.2	90.85 ± 14.60	μmol/L	[17–81]
Urea	6.28 ± 0.66	7.07 ± 0.51	mmol/L	[5.36–13.92]
Bun:Cre	22 ± 9	20 ± 4		
PHOS	3.62 ± 0.26	3.45 ± 0.23	mmol/L	[1.71–3.64]
Calcium	2.68 ± 0.19	2.49 ± 0.11	mmol/L	[1.47–2.96]
Sodium	174.42 ± 6.12	173.21 ± 5.16	mmol/L	[145–174]
Potassium	8.33 ± 0.34	8.23 ± 0.35	mmol/L	[6.5–10.5]
Na:K	21 ± 1	21 ± 1		
T-Protein	58.92 ± 3.68	57.33 ± 1.98	g/L	[33–76]
Albumin	29.06 ± 2.037	27.75 ± 1.31	g/L	[26–54]
Globulin	29.86 ± 3.497	29.58 ± 1.62	g/L	[20–38]
ALB:GLOB	1 ± 0.2	0.93 ± 0.1		
ALT	31.62 ± 4.89	36.1 ± 8.86	U/L	[14–140]
ALP	80.3 ± 10.52	65.84 ± 10.69	U/L	[46–291]
AMYL	1072.03 ± 176.07	1138.10 ± 87.99	U/L	[200–2500]
T-Bilirubin	4.94 ± 2.09	4.82 ± 1.53	μmol/L	[1.71–15.39]
CHOL	4.16 ± 0.87	4.19 ± 0.45	mmol/L	[0.9–5.66]
TBA	2.12 ± 1.63	1.23 ± 0.64	μmol/L	[0–15]

Table S2. Antibody list for spectral flow cytometry

Antibody list for the ex vivo immunological analysis				
Fluorochrome	Marker	Dilution	Company	reference number
APC	Arginase 1	400	invitrogen	17-3697-82
Biotin	CD103	200	Biolegend	121404
BV510	CD11b	1500	Biolegend	101263
PE-Cy5.5	CD11c	1800	invitrogen	35-0114-82
PerCP-eFlour 710	CD163	500	invitrogen	46-1631-82
BUV 661	CD19	400	BD Biosciences	612971
BV480	CD204	200	BD Biosciences	748084
AlexaFluor700	CD206	600	BioLegend	141734
BV 650	CD25	100	BioLegend	102038
R718	CD27	200	BD Biosciences	752216
BV 785	CD279	200	BioLegend	135225
APC	CD301b	200	BioLegend	146814
APC Fire 810	CD38	400	BioLegend	102746
AF647	CD39	200	BioLegend	143807
PerCP-eFlour710	CD39	500	invitrogen	46-0391-80
BUV496	CD4	250	BD Biosciences	612952
BUV737	CD44	1200	BD Biosciences	612799
BUV395	CD45	200	BD Biosciences	564279
Biotin	CD45.1	100	Biolegend	110703
PE-Cy7	CD45.2	100	Biolegend	109829
FITC	CD45.2	100	BD Biosciences	553772
BUV 805	CD49d	200	BD Biosciences	741925
BV570	CD62L	200	Biolegend	104433
BV605	CD64	100	Biolegend	139323
BUV395	CD69	100	BD Biosciences	740220
BB660-P	CD73	200	BD Biosciences	624295
BV 421	CD8	200	Biolegend	100738
BV750	CD88	200	BD Biosciences	747227
BUV 805	CD8a	200	BD Biosciences	612898
BV 421	CTLA4	200	Biolegend	106312
PE-Dazzle 594	CX3CR1	100	Biolegend	149013
BV785	CX3CR1	400	Biolegend	149029
PerCP-Cy5.5	CXCR3	100	invitrogen	45-1831-80
biotin	CXCR5	100	BD Biosciences	551960

APC/Fire750	F4/80	400	Biolegend	123151
PE	FoxP3	200	invitrogen	12-5773-82
PE-Cy5.5	Foxp3	200	invitrogen	35-5773-82
BUV563	GITR	400	BD Biosciences	741425
Pacific blue	Granzyme B	50	Biolegend	515408
BV750	ICOS	200	Biolegend	313558
BV480	Ki67	200	BD Biosciences	566109
APC-Cy7	KLRG1	400	Biolegend	138426
PE-Dazzle594	KLRG1	400	Biolegend	138423
BV 711	Ly6C	2000	Biolegend	128037
BUV563	Ly6G	400	BD Biosciences	565707
PE-Cy7	MertK	200	invitrogen	25-5751-82
Pacific Blue	MHCII	500	Biolegend	107620
BV711	NK1.1	150	BioLegend	108745
BB700	NK1.1	100	BD Biosciences	566502
BV605	PD1	100	BioLegend	135220
Superbright 780	PDL1	100	invitrogen	78-5982-62
PE	PDL1	200	invitrogen	12-5982-81
PE-Cy7	Sirpa	800	BioLegend	144008
BV421	Streptavidin	500	BioLegend	405226
BB630-P	Streptavidin	400	BD Biosciences	customized
BUV395	Streptavidin	400	BD Biosciences	564176
AF488	TCF1	400	Cell Signaling Technology	6444S
PE-Cy5	TCR beta	2500	BioLegend	109210
BUV615	TCRgd	200	BD Biosciences	751183
APC	TIM-3	400	BioLegend	119705
PE-Fire810	TIM-3	400	BioLegend	119745
PE	TOX	200	Miltenyi	130-120-785
BV 650	XCR1	800	BioLegend	148220

Table S3. Overlap protein list from proteomics analysis

Protein overlaps between experiment conditions		
BMDM_Co-culture	CT-2A_Co-culture	BMDM_Control
Fth1	Fth1	Fth1
Stab1	Stab1	Siglec1
Siglec1	Lbr	Serpinb2
Myo1c	Myo1f	Lyn
Pfdn2	Tjp2	Hnrnpul2
Ptgs2	Arid1b	Aimp1
Myo6	Smarca4	Myo1g
Riox2	Hspb1	H2afy
Gtse1	Rpl28	Atp6v1c1
Nup85	Sh2b1	Parp12
Eif3k	Taldo1	Lrp1
Wdr3	Rps19	Rbm6
Man2b1		Ctbp2
		Tuba4a
		Septin7
		Mpeg1
		Aldoat1
		Acs14
		Rpl34

Table S4. Patient samples for image-based functional profiling

Patient No.	Clinical identifier	Sex	Age	Histology	Grade	Status	IDH	MGMT promoter	EGFR	GBM subtype
Pat. 1	BTB677	Male	58	GBM	IV	primary	WT	unmethylated	not amplified	classical
Pat. 2	BTB685	Male	63	GBM	IV	primary	WT	unmethylated	not amplified	proneural
Pat. 3	BTB687	Female	54	GBM	IV	primary	WT	methylated	amplified	proneural
Pat. 4	BTB676	Male	71	GBM	IV	primary	WT	methylated	amplified	classical
Pat. 5	BTB691	Male	63	GBM	IV	primary	WT	unmethylated	not amplified	proneural
Pat. 6	BTB692	Male	70	GBM	IV	primary	WT	methylated	amplified	classical
Pat. 7	BTB704	Male	62	Not available	I-II	primary	WT	unmethylated	not amplified	Not available
Pat. 8	BTB705	Female	78	GBM	IV	primary	WT	methylated	amplified	classical
Pat. 9	BTB688	Female	72	GBM	IV	primary	WT	methylated	not amplified	mesenchymal
Pat. 10	BTB709	Not available	Not available	Not available						
Patient No.	Clinical identifier	Sex	Age	IDH	MGMT promoter	EGFRvIII mutation	EGFR	GBM subtype		
Pat. 11	BTB728	Not available								
Pat. 12	BTB639	Female	55	WT	Methylated	Detected	Amplified	Classical		
Pat. 13	BTB685	Male	63	WT	unmethylated		not amplified	Proneural		
Pat. 14	BTB676	Male	71	WT	Methylated	Detected	Amplified	Classical		
Pat. 15	BTB691	Male	63	WT	unmethylated	Not detected	not amplified	Proneural		
Pat. 16	BTB692	Male	80	WT	Methylated	Detected	Amplified	RTK II		
Pat. 17	BTB635	Male	64	WT	Methylated	Detected	Amplified	Classical		
Pat. 18	BTB685	Male	63	WT	unmethylated		not amplified	proneural		
Pat. 19	BTB709	Not available								
Pat. 20	BTB739	Male	59	WT	Methylated	Detected	Amplified	Classical		

Movie S1. Time-lapse fluorescence microscopy video of CT-2A-zsGreen glioma cells co-cultured with control BMDMs. Representative images from a 48-hour co-culture period showing CT-2A-zsGreen glioma cells (green) and control BMDMs labeled with Violet CellTrace (blue). Scale bar, 100 μm .

Movie S2. Time-lapse fluorescence microscopy video of CT-2A-zsGreen glioma cells co-cultured with MDC-735. Representative images from a 48-hour co-culture period showing CT-2A-zsGreen glioma cells (green) and MDC-735 labeled with Violet CellTrace (blue). Scale bar, 100 μm .

Movie S3. Time-lapse confocal microscopy illustrating direct interaction of HMDM and LN-229 glioma cells in co-culture. The video captures the dynamics of F-actin reorganization outlining the borders of cells initiating contact.

Movie S4. Time-lapse confocal microscopy video illustrating HFt-AF488 transfer from HMDM to LN-229 glioma cells. The video captures the dynamics of HFt-AF488 transfer, showcasing the appearance of AF488 signal in LN-229 cells at the point of direct cell-cell contact with HMDM-HFt-AF488.

Data file S1. All individual-level tabular data for all data in the manuscript.

Data file S2. Plasmid sequence.